

CAN CORPORATIONS BE TRUSTED?
**VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE AND THE LIMITS OF NON-COERCIVE BUSINESS
REGULATION**

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ABSTRACT

This Article extends the voluntary compliance framework developed in *Can the Public Be Trusted? The Promise and Perils of Voluntary Compliance* to the corporate context. While recent scholarship has explored when states can rely on non-coercive regulatory approaches with individual citizens, comparatively little attention has been paid to whether these insights translate to business entities. This Article argues that corporations present both greater challenges and greater opportunities for voluntary compliance regimes. On one hand, the instrumental orientation of corporate decision-making, amplified by fiduciary duties and competitive pressures, may systematically undermine the intrinsic motivations that voluntary compliance frameworks depend upon. Drawing on behavioral ethics research, demonstrating that organizational settings can serve as “hotbeds for unethicity,” this Article identifies structural features of corporate environments that impede genuine voluntary compliance. On the other hand, corporations possess characteristics that facilitate trust-based regulation: they are repeat players sensitive to reputational consequences, operate through transparent bureaucratic processes amenable to monitoring, and cannot claim violations of personal autonomy when past behavior informs regulatory treatment. This Article synthesizes these competing considerations into a differentiated framework for corporate regulation, identifying the conditions under which non-coercive approaches are most likely to succeed across securities regulation, environmental compliance, and corporate governance more broadly.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between the state and its regulated subjects has long oscillated between coercion and cooperation. In recent decades, regulatory theory increasingly emphasized the potential of non-coercive approaches, from responsive regulation to behavioral nudges, as alternatives to traditional command-and-control frameworks.¹ This scholarly movement reflects a growing recognition that deterrence-based enforcement faces inherent limitations: monitoring costs are prohibitive, sanctions often prove ineffective or counterproductive, and coercive approaches may crowd out the intrinsic motivations that produce the highest quality compliance.² Yet the question remains: can the public be trusted to voluntarily comply with legal requirements when enforcement is relaxed?

My recent book, *Can the Public Be Trusted? The Promise and Perils of Voluntary Compliance*, addresses this question across multiple regulatory domains, examining when and how states can effectively employ trust-based regulatory strategies with individual citizens.³ The book develops a comprehensive framework for understanding the conditions under which

¹ See IAN AYRES & JOHN BRAITHWAITE, *RESPONSIVE REGULATION: TRANSCENDING THE DEREGULATION DEBATE* 4 (Donald R. Harris et al. eds., 1992); Valerie Braithwaite, *Responsive Regulation and Taxation: Introduction*, 29 L. & POL'Y 3, 9–10 (2007); Jenny Job, Andrew Stout & Rachael Smith, *Culture Change in Three Taxation Administrations: From Command-and-Control to Responsive Regulation*, 29 L. & POL'Y 84, 98 (2007).

² See Bruno S. Frey & Felix Oberholzer-Gee, *The Cost of Price Incentives: An Empirical Analysis of Motivation Crowding-Out*, 87 AM. ECON. REV. 746, 753–54 (1997); Kristen Underhill, *When Extrinsic Incentives Displace Intrinsic Motivation: Designing Legal Carrots and Sticks to Confront the Challenge of Motivational Crowding-Out*, 33 YALE J. ON REG. 213, 278 (2016).

³ YUVAL FELDMAN, *CAN THE PUBLIC BE TRUSTED?: ON THE PROMISE AND PERILS OF VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE* 1–3 (2025).

voluntary compliance is likely to succeed. The framework analyzes the intricate interplay between intrinsic motivation, cultural context, and regulatory design across tax compliance, environmental regulation, and public health mandates.⁴ The analysis reveals that voluntary compliance is not a binary phenomenon but exists along a spectrum, with its effectiveness depending critically on contextual factors that regulators must carefully consider.⁵ However, the book primarily focuses on individual compliance, leaving open a question of significant practical importance: to what extent can these insights be translated to the corporate context?

This Article tackles this question by examining whether and when states can rely on non-coercive approaches in regulating business entities. The inquiry is both theoretically significant and practically urgent, as much of contemporary regulatory activity targets corporations rather than individuals. Securities regulation, environmental protection, antitrust enforcement, consumer protection, and occupational safety all primarily concern corporate conduct. If voluntary compliance frameworks cannot be extended to business entities, their practical applicability is severely constrained.⁶ The question becomes even more pressing as governments worldwide grapple with limited enforcement resources and seek more efficient regulatory strategies.

The corporate context, which wasn't the focus of *Can the Public be Trusted?*, presents distinctive challenges for voluntary compliance theory. Corporations are, by design, instrumental

⁴ *See id.*

⁵ *Id.*, 253, 297.

⁶ *Id.*, 26; also: Chater, Nick, and George Loewenstein. "The i-frame and the s-frame: How focusing on individual-level solutions has led behavioral public policy astray." *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 46 (2023): 1–26. s

actors. Unlike individuals who may comply with legal requirements out of civic duty, moral conviction, or social pressure, corporations exist to maximize shareholder value.⁷ Their decision-making processes are structured around economic calculation and bound by fiduciary obligations to pursue profit-maximizing strategies.⁸ This instrumental orientation suggests that corporations will comply with legal requirements when, and only when, compliance serves their financial interests—precisely the behavioral pattern that voluntary compliance frameworks seek to transcend. The challenge is particularly acute because corporate decision-making involves multiple actors with potentially divergent incentives, creating agency problems that complicate any analysis of compliance motivation.

Moreover, research in behavioral ethics, including my own work with Adi Libson and Gideon Parchomovsky on *Corporate Law for Good People*, suggests that organizational settings may actually amplify the cognitive biases and self-serving rationalizations that lead otherwise ethical individuals to engage in misconduct.⁹ The diffusion of responsibility in corporate hierarchies, the pressure of competitive markets, and the psychological distance between decision-makers and the consequences of their decisions create conditions that may render corporations as hotbeds of unethically.¹⁰ If good people often behave unethically in

⁷ See Milton Friedman, *A Friedman Doctrine-- The Social Responsibility of Business Is to Increase Its Profits*, N.Y. TIMES (Sep. 13, 1970), <https://www.nytimes.com/1970/09/13/archives/a-friedman-doctrine-the-social-responsibility-of-business-is-to.html> [<https://perma.cc/3JPE-JSMA>].

⁸ See Leo E. Strine, Jr., *Our continuing struggle with the Idea that For-Profit Corporations Seek Profit*, 47 Wake Forest L. Rev. 135, 146-148 (2012).

⁹ Yuval Feldman, Adi Libson & Gideon Parchomovsky, *Corporate Law for Good People*, 115 NW. U. L. REV. 1125, 1125 (2021).

¹⁰ *Id.* at 1130.

organizational contexts without recognizing the ethical dimensions of their conduct, the prospects for trust-based corporate regulation appear dim.

Yet the picture is not uniformly pessimistic. Corporations possess certain characteristics that may make them more amenable to trust-based regulation than individuals in important respects. Corporations are repeat players in regulatory interactions, with long time horizons and ongoing relationships with regulatory authorities.¹¹ Corporations are often highly sensitive to reputational consequences, which can impact their corporate behavior more than formal legal sanctions.¹² Their operations are typically more transparent and documented than individual conduct, making monitoring less costly and intrusive. Finally, corporations cannot claim the autonomy-based objections that constrain how states may treat individuals.¹³ Regulators need not worry about violating corporate dignity when they use past compliance history to inform future regulatory treatment.¹⁴ These features suggest that under appropriate conditions, trust-based regulatory approaches may not only be viable for corporations but may be more effective than in the individual context.

This Article proceeds in four parts. Part I, *The Promise Of Voluntary Compliance*, briefly summarizes the theoretical foundations of voluntary compliance, drawing on the framework

¹¹ See Tracey Swift, *Trust, Reputation and Corporate Accountability to Stakeholders*, 10 BUS. ETHICS: EUR. REV. 16, 22–23 (2001).

¹² See Hean Tat Keh & Yi Xie, *Corporate Reputation and Customer Behavioral Intentions: The Roles of Trust, Identification and Commitment*, 38 INDUS. MARKETING MGMT. 732, 732 (2009) (recognizing that corporate reputation may serve as an intangible asset capable of strengthening a firm's competitive position).

¹³ See YUVAL FELDMAN, *CAN THE PUBLIC BE TRUSTED?: ON THE PROMISE AND PERILS OF VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE*, 103 (2025)

¹⁴ See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 165–185 (discussing technology-driven differentiated enforcement based on past behavior); See Grear, Anna. *Redirecting human rights: Facing the challenge of corporate legal humanity*, (2010).

developed in *Can the Public Be Trusted?* Part I examines the slippery slope framework, procedural justice theory, responsive regulation, and the motivational postures paradigm that provides the conceptual architecture for understanding when and why voluntary compliance succeeds. Part II, *The Skeptical Case: Why Corporations May Resist Voluntary Compliance*, presents the skeptical case, which examines why corporations may be particularly resistant to non-coercive regulatory approaches. Drawing on insights from behavioral ethics and organizational behavior, Part II identifies the structural features of corporate decision-making that impede the development of intrinsic compliance motivation. Part III, *The Hopeful Case: Conditions For Corporate Voluntary Compliance*, develops the hopeful case, which identifies conditions under which corporate voluntary compliance may succeed. Part III examines reputational mechanisms, repeat-player dynamics, private ordering arrangements, and existing voluntary compliance programs to demonstrate that trust-based approaches can work with corporations under appropriate conditions. Part IV, *A Differentiated Framework For Corporate Regulation*, synthesizes these competing considerations into a differentiated framework for corporate regulation, offering guidance on when trust-based approaches are appropriate across different regulatory domains and examining the role of technology in enabling differentiated enforcement.

II. THE PROMISE OF VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE

A. Theoretical Foundations

Before examining how voluntary compliance principles apply to corporations, it is necessary to review the theoretical foundations of this approach as developed in the individual context in *Can the Public be Trusted*. The core insight of voluntary compliance theory is that the quality and sustainability of compliance depend not merely on whether regulated parties obey

legal requirements, but on why they do so.¹⁵ When individuals comply primarily because of the threat of sanctions, their compliance tends to be minimal, grudging, and unstable.¹⁶ Individuals will reduce compliance when the probability of detection falls, exploit ambiguities in legal requirements to avoid obligations while remaining technically within the law, and satisfy formal regulatory criteria without pursuing the substantive goals the regulation was designed to achieve.¹⁷ By contrast, when individuals comply because they believe legal requirements are legitimate, feel a civic duty to obey, or because they have internalized the values underlying legal mandates, their compliance is more robust, consistent, and likely to exceed minimum requirements.¹⁸

This distinction between externally and intrinsically motivated compliance has been developed most extensively in the tax compliance literature, particularly through Erich Kirchler's influential "slippery slope" framework.¹⁹ Kirchler and his colleagues argue that tax compliance

¹⁵ See Yuval Feldman, *The Complexity of Disentangling Intrinsic and Extrinsic Compliance Motivations: Theoretical and Empirical Insights from the Behavioral Analysis of Law*, 35 WASH. U. J.L. & POL'Y 11, 12–13 (2011) (demonstrating that intrinsically motivated compliance produces higher quality and more durable behavioral change than coerced compliance, but that poorly designed enforcement can undermine the very motivation it depends on).

¹⁶ See YUVAL FELDMAN, CAN THE PUBLIC BE TRUSTED?: ON THE PROMISE AND PERILS OF VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE, 7-8 (2025); Gunningham, Neil, Robert A. Kagan, and Dorothy Thornton. *Social license and environmental protection: Why businesses go beyond compliance* Law & Social Inquiry 29.2 (2004): 307–341.

¹⁷ See Robert Cooter, *Do Good Laws Make Good Citizens? An Economic Analysis of Internalized Norms*, 86 VA. L. REV. 1577, 1601 (2000); See YUVAL FELDMAN, CAN THE PUBLIC BE TRUSTED?: ON THE PROMISE AND PERILS OF VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE, 53(2025); see also Cerasoli, Christopher P., Jessica M. Nicklin, and Michael T. Ford. "Intrinsic motivation and extrinsic incentives jointly predict performance: a 40-year meta-analysis." *Psychological bulletin* 140.4 (2014): 980.

¹⁸ See TOM R. TYLER, WHY PEOPLE OBEY THE LAW 7 (1990).

¹⁹ See Erich Kirchler, Erik Hoelzl & Ingrid Wahl, *Enforced Versus Voluntary Tax Compliance: The "Slippery Slope" Framework*, 29 J. ECON. PSYCH. 210, 212 (2008).

depends on two independent dimensions: the power of tax authorities (their capacity to detect and punish evasion) and the trust that citizens place in those authorities.²⁰ High power produces enforced compliance, while high trust produces voluntary compliance²¹. The framework suggests that optimal regulatory outcomes require attention to both dimensions, but that trust-based voluntary compliance offers significant advantages over power-based enforced compliance: it is less costly to achieve, more stable over time, and produces higher quality adherence to regulatory objectives.²² Importantly, the framework recognizes that power and trust are not simply substitutes; under certain conditions, the exercise of power can actually undermine trust, creating a “slippery slope” toward an enforcement-dependent relationship between regulators and regulated parties.²³

Tom Tyler’s procedural justice research provides complementary support for this framework.²⁴ Tyler’s extensive empirical work demonstrates that when individuals perceive authorities as fair, transparent, and respectful, compliance rates increase substantially, often exceeding what can be achieved through deterrence alone.²⁵ This finding holds across diverse

²⁰ See Aloys Prinz, Stephan Muehlbacher & Erich Kirchler, *The Slippery Slope Framework on Tax Compliance: An Attempt to Formalization*, 40 J. ECON. PSYCH. 20, 21 (2014).

²¹ See Ingrid Wahl, Barbara Kastlunger & Erich Kirchler, *Trust in Authorities and Power to Enforce Tax Compliance: An Empirical Analysis of the “Slippery Slope Framework,”* 32 L. & Pol’y 383, 385, 392-97 (2010) (finding experimentally that trust increases voluntary compliance while power increases enforced compliance, and that high power combined with low trust produces greater strategic taxpaying behavior).

²² See Stephan Muehlbacher, Erich Kirchler & Herbert Schwarzenberger, *Voluntary Versus Enforced Tax Compliance: Empirical Evidence for the “Slippery Slope” Framework*, 32 EUR. J. L. & ECON. 89, 96 (2011).

²³ See *id.*

²⁴ See TYLER, *supra* note 18, at 7.

²⁵ See Jonathan Jackson et al., *Why Do People Comply with the Law? Legitimacy and the Influence of Legal Institutions*, 52 BRIT. J. CRIMINOLOGY 1051, 1051–52 (2012).

regulatory contexts, from policing to environmental protection to corporate governance, suggesting underlying psychological mechanisms that transcend specific domains.²⁶ The key insight is that legitimacy, rather than fear, may be the more powerful lever for securing compliance.²⁷ When people believe that authorities are acting fairly and in the public interest, they are more willing to defer to those authorities' judgments about appropriate behavior, even when compliance is costly or inconvenient²⁸.

The responsive regulation framework developed by Ian Ayres and John Braithwaite offers a practical approach to implementing these insights.²⁹ Their influential “enforcement pyramid” begins with persuasion and voluntary compliance at the base, escalating to warning letters, civil penalties, criminal prosecution, and ultimately license revocation at the peak³⁰. The key insight is that the credible threat of escalation makes persuasion more effective, while the preference for persuasion preserves the legitimacy and efficiency benefits of voluntary

²⁶ See Kristina Murphy & Tom Tyler, *Procedural Justice and Compliance Behaviour: The Mediating Role of Emotions*, 38 EUR. J. SOC. PSYCH. 652, 652 (2008); see also Glenn D. Walters & P. Colin Bolger, *Procedural Justice Perceptions, Legitimacy Beliefs, and Compliance with the Law: A Meta-Analysis*, 15 J. EXPERIMENTAL CRIMINOLOGY 341, 341–42 (2019) ((synthesizing sixty-four studies and finding significant positive relationships between procedural justice perceptions, legitimacy beliefs, and legal compliance, with path analysis showing that legitimacy mediates the relationship between procedural justice and compliance).).

²⁷ Tyler, T. R., & Jackson, J. (2014). Popular legitimacy and the exercise of legal authority: Motivating compliance, cooperation, and engagement. *Psychology, Public Policy, and Law*, 20(1), 78–95. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034514>

²⁸ See Tom R. Tyler, *Psychological Perspectives on Legitimacy and Legitimation*, 57 Ann. Rev. Psych. 375, 389-92 (2006) (arguing that legitimacy-based regulation provides a more effective and sustainable basis for legal compliance than deterrence, since people who view authorities as legitimate internalize the obligation to obey rather than responding only to the threat of sanctions).

²⁹ See AYRES & BRAITHWAITE, *supra* note 1, at 4.

³⁰ Id at So for the *Id.* pincite, I'd suggest: *Id.* at 35-38.

compliance.³¹ Responsive regulation thus does not naively assume that all regulated parties will comply voluntarily; rather, it reserves coercive measures for those who prove untrustworthy while treating the majority of regulated parties as potentially cooperative actors. This approach has been influential in regulatory practice across multiple domains, from tax administration to environmental protection to occupational safety.³²

The empirical evidence supporting voluntary approaches is compelling. Research in behavioral law and economics demonstrates that intrinsically motivated compliance often produces higher quality outcomes than externally enforced behavior. When individuals comply voluntarily, they tend to embrace the spirit rather than merely the letter of regulations. This distinction proves particularly crucial in complex regulatory domains where complete monitoring is impossible and the quality of compliance matters as much as its occurrence. From an operational perspective, voluntary compliance offers significant advantages. It dramatically reduces monitoring and enforcement costs, allowing regulatory agencies to redirect resources toward education, support, and systemic improvements. Perhaps more importantly, it transforms the regulatory relationship from one characterized by suspicion and resistance to one built on mutual respect and shared objectives.

³¹ See John Braithwaite, *The Essence of Responsive Regulation*, 44 U.B.C. L. REV. 475, 482 (2011).

³² See Judith Freedman, *Responsive Regulation, Risk and Rules: Applying the Theory to Tax Practice*, 44 U.B.C. L. REV. 627, 627 (2011); see also Vibeke Lehmann Nielsen & Christine Parker, *Testing Responsive Regulation in Regulatory Enforcement*, 3 REGUL. & GOVERNANCE 376, 376 (2009) (stating how responsive regulation is a prominent framework for understanding how enforcement actions can encourage compliance).

B. Voluntary Compliance in Practice

How do these theoretical frameworks translate into regulatory practice? *Can the Public Be Trusted?* examines voluntary compliance strategies across three key domains: tax administration, environmental regulation, and public health.³³ Each domain presents distinct challenges and opportunities for trust-based approaches, and the comparative analysis reveals important lessons about the conditions under which voluntary compliance is most likely to succeed.

In tax compliance, voluntary strategies include simplified filing processes, educational campaigns about civic duty, and cooperative compliance programs where tax authorities work collaboratively with taxpayers to ensure accurate reporting.³⁴ Some tax administrations have adopted or considered service-oriented tax administration approaches that emphasizes support alongside enforcement, treating taxpayers as customers rather than solely as potential violators.³⁵ The empirical evidence on these approaches is mixed with generally limited overall effects but some encouraging findings: moral appeals and service-oriented approaches can increase compliance among certain groups of taxpayers, though their effectiveness varies significantly across cultural and institutional contexts.³⁶ Studies have found that normative appeals emphasizing civic duty and the social benefits of tax revenue can improve compliance among

³³ See FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 8.

³⁴ See *generally id.* at 205–25 ((examining voluntary compliance strategies in tax administration, including simplified filing, normative appeals, and cooperative compliance programs between tax authorities and taxpayers).

³⁵ See Keith Snavelly, *Governmental Policies to Reduce Tax Evasion: Coerced Behavior Versus Services and Values Development*, 23 POL’Y SCIS. 57, 57–58 (1990).

³⁶ See Marsha Blumenthal, Charlie Christian & Joel Slemrod, *Do Normative Appeals Affect Tax Compliance? Evidence from a Controlled Experiment in Minnesota*, 54 NAT’L TAX J. 125, 125 (2001) (conducting a controlled field experiment with the Minnesota Department of Revenue in which normative appeal letters were sent to approximately 40,000 taxpayers, finding little evidence of an overall treatment effect on compliance but detecting significant effects among certain subgroups of taxpayers)).

certain populations, while having little effect or even backfiring among others³⁷. This heterogeneity underscores the importance of understanding contextual factors when designing voluntary compliance programs.

Environmental regulation has seen innovative voluntary approaches such as emissions trading schemes, public recognition programs for green businesses, and collaborative watershed management where stakeholders collectively develop and implement conservation plans.³⁸ Programs such as Energy Star certification demonstrates how voluntary labeling can, under certain conditions, drive market-based environmental improvements without relying solely on traditional command-and-control regulation.³⁹ Voluntary sustainability standards have become increasingly common in global value chains, employing three main mechanisms to foster

³⁷ See Michael Hallsworth, John A. List, Robert D. Metcalfe & Ivo Vlaev, *The Behavioralist as Tax Collector: Using Natural Field Experiments to Enhance Tax Compliance*, 148 J. Pub. Econ. 14, 14-15 (2017) (conducting two large-scale field experiments with over 200,000 UK taxpayers and finding that social norm messages in reminder letters significantly increased payment rates for overdue tax, with the most effective message producing a 5.1 percentage point increase in compliance); *but see* Marsha Blumenthal, Charles Christian & Joel Slemrod, *Do Normative Appeals Affect Tax Compliance? Evidence from a Controlled Experiment in Minnesota*, 54 Nat'l Tax J. 125, 125 (2001) (finding little evidence of an overall treatment effect from normative appeal letters sent to Minnesota taxpayers, though detecting significant effects among certain subgroups).

³⁸ See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 226–46 ((surveying voluntary environmental compliance strategies, including emissions trading, public recognition programs, and collaborative stakeholder governance, and examining the conditions under which non-coercive approaches produce environmental improvements beyond what command-and-control regulation achieves).).

³⁹ See Aseem Prakash & Matthew Potoski, *Voluntary Environmental Programs: A Comparative Perspective*, 31 J. Pol'y Analysis & Mgmt. 123, 124-26 (2012) (analyzing the design and effectiveness of government-sponsored voluntary environmental programs, including certification and labeling schemes such as Energy Star, and identifying the conditions under which such programs induce firms to produce environmental goods beyond legal requirements).

compliance: enforcement, market incentives, and capacity-building.⁴⁰ Research has shown that while enforcement appears necessary across voluntary sustainability standards, there is significant variation in how market incentives and capacity-building mechanisms are used and combined, reflecting different approaches to generating compliance across contexts⁴¹. Over-reliance on command-and-control regulation can undermine the intrinsic motivation of regulated firms to exceed minimum requirements, particularly in environmental contexts, as there is often a significant gap between simply satisfying regulatory thresholds and adopting innovative modifications that truly improve environmental outcomes.. *Can the Public Be Trusted?* identifies several key findings that emerge from this cross-domain analysis. First, voluntary compliance is not an all-or-nothing proposition; the relevant question then is how to calibrate a mix of voluntary and coercive approaches to fit different populations and contexts.⁴² Second, the effectiveness of voluntary compliance strategies depends critically on cultural context; what works in one jurisdiction may fail in another due to differences in social trust, attitudes toward authority, and prevailing norms.⁴³ Third, voluntary compliance and

⁴⁰ See Charline Depoorter & Axel Marx, *Fostering Compliance with Voluntary Sustainability Standards Through Institutional Design: An Analytic Framework and Empirical Application*, 18 REGUL. & GOVERNANCE 1132, 1148 (2024).

⁴¹ See *id.* at 1140-48 (applying the framework to thirteen agrifood and forestry voluntary sustainability standards and finding that while enforcement mechanisms are consistently present across standards, there is considerable variation in the use of market incentives and capacity-building mechanisms).

⁴² See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 247–72 (arguing that voluntary compliance exists along a spectrum rather than as a binary choice, and developing a framework for calibrating the balance between trust-based and coercive regulatory approaches to match the compliance dispositions, institutional contexts, and risk profiles of different regulated populations).

⁴³ See generally *id.* at 143–64 ((examining how cultural context shapes the effectiveness of voluntary compliance strategies, showing that differences in social trust, attitudes toward governmental authority, and prevailing norms of cooperation across jurisdictions produce

enforcement are not necessarily in tension; the credible threat of enforcement can actually enhance the effectiveness of voluntary approaches by distinguishing between trustworthy and untrustworthy regulated parties.⁴⁴

C. The Motivational Postures Framework

Continuing the discussion on procedural justice and legitimacy on the individual level, the paradigm of motivational postures extends this model to provide a more comprehensive understanding of compliance motivation. In their influential research on motivational postures, Valerie Braithwaite, Kristina Murphy, and Monika Reinhart argue that “the most effective regulatory outcome is achieved when the regulatory process can dampen the ‘taking control’ and ‘feeling oppressed’ sensibilities, and strengthen the ‘thinking morally’ sensibility.”⁴⁵ This framework focuses on the relationship between the regulated parties and the regulatory system, looking beyond the legal technicalities of the written law to the psychological factors that drive human behavior which leads to real-world compliance.

Braithwaite identified five different motivational postures that individuals adopt toward regulatory authorities: commitment, capitulation, resistance, disengagement, and game playing.⁴⁶ Commitment involves genuine belief in the regulatory system’s goals; committed citizens need only light-touch engagement. Capitulation represents acceptance of requirements without

significant variation in the success of trust-based regulatory approaches that might otherwise appear universally promising).

⁴⁴ See Netta Barak-Corren & Yael Kariv-Teitelbaum, *Behavioral Responsive Regulation: Bringing Together Responsive Regulation and Behavioral Public Policy*, 15 REGUL. & GOVERNANCE S163, S178 (2021).

⁴⁵ Valerie Braithwaite, Kristina Murphy & Monika Reinhart, *Taxation Threat, Motivational Postures, and Responsive Regulation*, 29 L. & POL’Y 137, 137 (2007).

⁴⁶ See *id.* at 138–39.

necessarily embracing the underlying goals. Resistance involves questioning and challenging authority while remaining engaged with the system. Disengagement reflects psychological withdrawal from the regulatory system entirely. Game playing involves strategic manipulation of rules for personal advantage. Different postures require different regulatory responses. For example, committed individuals benefit from trust-based approaches, while game players require credible deterrence to ensure compliance.

This framework has been applied in context of Australian agriculture and environmental regulation. The study found that farmers' motivational postures toward regulators strongly predicted compliance and beyond-compliance behavior, reflecting differences in regulatory alignment.⁴⁷ Farmers with commitment postures exceeded requirements, while those with resistance postures complied minimally despite monitoring from regulators. Research showed that confrontational enforcement and conflict with regulatory authorities are associated with heightened resistance postures demonstrating the potential risks of regulatory approaches that intensify feelings of oppression and reduce moral alignment.⁴⁸ The framework suggests that

⁴⁷ See Robyn Bartel & Elaine Barclay, *Motivational Postures and Compliance with Environmental Law in Australian Agriculture*, 27 J. Rural Stud. 260, 260-61 (2011) (finding that farmers' resistance postures toward environmental regulators were strongly associated with the degree of perceived regulatory overreach, and that such postures predicted minimal compliance regardless of monitoring intensity); see also Valerie Braithwaite, Kristina Murphy & Monika Reinhart, *Taxation Threat, Motivational Postures, and Responsive Regulation*, 29 L. & Pol'y 137, 152-53 (2007) (finding that taxpayers subjected to aggressive enforcement action by the Australian Tax Office exhibited heightened resistance and desire to challenge the authority's decisions, suggesting that a more responsive regulatory approach might have produced better long-term compliance outcomes).

⁴⁸ See Valerie Braithwaite, Kristina Murphy & Monika Reinhart, *Taxation Threat, Motivational Postures, and Responsive Regulation*, 29 L. & Pol'y 137, 152-53 (2007) (finding that taxpayers subjected to aggressive enforcement by the Australian Tax Office exhibited heightened resistance and a persistent desire to challenge the authority's decisions, and suggesting that a

understanding motivational postures is essential for designing effective regulatory strategies, approaches that work for committed individuals may be counterproductive for game players, and vice versa.

III. These insights provide the foundation for examining whether voluntary compliance frameworks can be extended to the corporate context. The following Parts explore both the challenges and opportunities that corporations present for trust-based regulation, drawing on the theoretical frameworks developed in *Can the Public Be Trusted?* with regards to individuals, while attending to the distinctive features of corporate decision-making and organizational behavior.⁴⁹ THE SKEPTICAL CASE: WHY CORPORATIONS MAY RESIST VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE

A. The Instrumental Logic of Corporate Decision-Making

The fundamental challenge to corporate voluntary compliance is the instrumental nature of corporate decision-making. Unlike individuals—who may comply with legal requirements for moral, social, or civic reasons independent of self-interest—corporations are designed to maximize shareholder value.⁵⁰ While the precise contours of corporate purpose remain contested, the prevailing legal and economic understanding holds that corporations exist primarily to

responsive regulatory approach would have produced more durable compliance); *see also* Robyn Bartel & Elaine Barclay, *Motivational Postures and Compliance with Environmental Law in Australian Agriculture*, 27 *J. Rural Stud.* 260, 268-70 (2011) (finding that farmers' resistance postures toward environmental regulators were strongly associated with perceived regulatory overreach, and that such postures predicted only minimal compliance regardless of enforcement intensity, while aligned postures predicted beyond-compliance behavior).

⁴⁹ *See infra* Parts III-V (examining, respectively, the structural features of corporate decision-making that impede voluntary compliance, the conditions under which trust-based corporate regulation may succeed, and a differentiated framework for calibrating regulatory approaches across domains).

⁵⁰ *See* Friedman, *supra* note 7.

generate returns for their investors.⁵¹ Corporate managers owe fiduciary duties to act in shareholders' interests, and competitive market pressures punish firms that pursue objectives other than profit maximization.⁵² This structural feature of corporate existence creates fundamental tensions with voluntary compliance theory, which depends on motivations beyond narrow self-interest.

The foundational insight of voluntary compliance theory is that compliance is motivated by intrinsic factors, belief in the legitimacy of legal requirements, sense of civic duty, or moral conviction, and that said compliance is more robust and sustainable than compliance motivated by fear of sanctions. But corporations, as artificial entities, cannot experience intrinsic motivation in the same way that individuals can. A corporation cannot believe in the justice of environmental regulations or feel a civic duty to pay taxes; at most, individual employees and managers can hold such beliefs, but the corporation as an entity remains as an instrumental actor pursuing its defined objectives.⁵³ The aggregation problem is severe: even if individual corporate

⁵¹ See Henry Hansmann & Reinier Kraakman, *The End of History for Corporate Law*, 89 GEO. L. J. 439, 439 (2001) (arguing that a broad consensus has emerged across jurisdictions that the corporate form is oriented toward shareholder interests, and that the principal regulatory challenge is the agency problem of ensuring that managers act in those interests rather than their own).

⁵² See Jean B. McGuire, Alison Sundgren & Thomas Schneeweis, *Corporate Social Responsibility and Firm Financial Performance*, 31 ACAD. MGMT. J. 854, 868 (1988 (examining the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance and finding that firms with strong social responsibility records tend to show stronger financial performance, but acknowledging that competitive market pressures constrain firms' willingness to deviate from profit-maximizing strategies)

⁵³ See generally Donald C. Langevoort, *Monitoring: The Behavioral Economics of Corporate Compliance with Law*, 2002 Colum. Bus. L. Rev. 71, 75-80 (examining the divergent compliance incentives between firms and their agents, and arguing that aggressive command-and-control monitoring may be less effective at producing compliance than attention to organizational norms, culture, and trust); Donald C. Langevoort, *Organized Illusions: A Behavioral Theory of Why Corporations Mislead Stock Market Investors (and Cause Other Social Harms)*, 146 U. Pa. L.

actors possess intrinsic compliance motivations, organizational structures and incentives may systematically override those individual motivations in favor of the corporation's instrumental objectives.

This does not mean that corporations will invariably evade legal requirements when they can do so profitably. Corporations comply with laws for many reasons beyond the threat of sanctions: to maintain valuable reputations, to respond to pressures from communities and stakeholders, to attract and retain employees who care about ethical conduct, to satisfy consumers who prefer to purchase from law-abiding firms, or because compliance is simply the path of least resistance in a complex regulatory environment.⁵⁴ But all of these reasons are ultimately instrumental; they tie compliance to corporate self-interest rather than to intrinsic commitment to legal and ethical values.

Rev. 101, 135-44 (1997) (arguing that corporate misconduct frequently arises not from individual bad actors but from predictable organizational dynamics, including competitive pressures and optimism biases embedded in corporate hierarchies, that systematically distort decision-making without conscious wrongdoing); Feldman, Libson & Parchomovsky, *supra* note 9, at 1145-49 (identifying structural features of corporate environments, including diffusion of responsibility, performance pressure, and repeated exposure to ethical ambiguity, that transform organizations into settings where individually ethical employees collectively produce unethical outcomes).

⁵⁴ See Robert A. Kagan, Neil Gunningham & Dorothy Thornton, *Explaining Corporate Environmental Performance: How Does Regulation Matter?*, 37 *L. & Soc'y Rev.* 51, 56-60 (2003) (identifying multiple motivations for corporate compliance beyond legal sanctions, including maintaining a "social license" to operate, satisfying consumer and investor expectations, retaining employees committed to responsible business practices, and following industry norms that make compliance the organizational default); see also Neil Gunningham, Robert A. Kagan & Dorothy Thornton, *Social License and Environmental Protection: Why Businesses Go Beyond Compliance*, 29 *L. & Soc. Inquiry* 307, 310-12 (2004) (finding that corporate environmental behavior is shaped not only by regulatory requirements and enforcement threats but also by reputational concerns, community pressure, and internal management norms that motivate compliance independent of formal sanctions).

The empirical evidence provides grounds for skepticism. Research on corporate tax avoidance demonstrates that corporations engage in sophisticated tax planning strategies to minimize their tax burdens, exploiting ambiguities in tax law and arbitraging across jurisdictions.⁵⁵ A study by Scott Dyreng and colleagues found that while the average statutory corporate tax rate was thirty percent, the effective tax rate after avoidance strategies was only twenty percent.⁵⁶ Moreover, firms that successfully maintain low effective tax rates do so for extended periods, suggesting that tax avoidance is a deliberate and sustained corporate strategy rather than an occasional opportunistic deviation.⁵⁷ This pattern of strategic avoidance is consistent with the instrumental model of corporate behavior and poses a serious challenge for trust-based regulatory approaches that assume some degree of intrinsic compliance motivation.

B. Trust, Toxic Corporate Culture, and the Risk of Opportunism

A core difficulty in extending voluntary compliance frameworks to corporations lies in the organizational dynamics that systematically weaken moral constraint. Unlike individuals, corporations do not possess intrinsic moral intuitions; they operate through incentive structures, hierarchical decision-making, and performance metrics that can crowd out ethical reflection. As a result, trust extended to corporations, by regulators, investors, or the public, may be strategically exploited rather than reciprocated.

⁵⁵ See Scott D. Dyreng, Michelle Hanlon & Edward L. Maydew, *Long-Run Corporate Tax Avoidance*, 83 ACCT. REV. 61, 62 (2008).

⁵⁶ *Id.* at 61.

⁵⁷ See *id.* at 79-80 ((finding that firms in the lowest quartile of effective tax rates sustain those low rates over periods of up to ten years, indicating that corporate tax avoidance reflects deliberate long-term strategic planning rather than isolated transactional decisions)).

Recent empirical work by Benjamin van Rooij and Adam Fine demonstrates how toxic corporate cultures normalize and entrench wrongdoing even among otherwise well-intentioned employees.⁵⁸ Studying major corporate scandals, van Rooij and Fine show that organizational environments frequently reward rule-breaking, marginalize compliance functions, and frame legal constraints as obstacles to be managed rather than norms to be respected.⁵⁹ In such settings, trust operates not as a moral signal but as a vulnerability. Where monitoring is relaxed or enforcement is delayed, firms may rationally interpret trust as an opportunity to advance organizational goals through evasion, deception, or boundary-pushing.⁶⁰

This insight aligns with broader behavioral ethics research documenting how organizations facilitate ethical fading, diffusion of responsibility, and normalization of deviance.⁶¹ When misconduct becomes routinized, employees may no longer perceive their actions as wrongful, even when they knowingly violate the law. Importantly, these dynamics do not require “bad actors.” They arise from structural features of corporate life, competitive pressure, internal silos, and short-term performance incentives that undermine intrinsic motivation to comply.⁶² From

⁵⁸ Benjamin van Rooij & Adam Fine, *Toxic Corporate Culture: Assessing Organizational Processes of Deviancy*, ADMIN. SCIS., Sep. 2018, at 1, 3.

⁵⁹ *See id.* at 25–30.

⁶⁰ *See id.* at 8-15.

⁶¹ *See* YUVAL FELDMAN, THE LAW OF GOOD PEOPLE: CHALLENGING STATES’ ABILITY TO REGULATE HUMAN BEHAVIOR 21–24 (2018). *See generally* Ann E. Tenbrunsel & David M. Messick, *Ethical Fading: The Role of Self-Deception in Unethical Behavior*, 17 SOC. JUST. RSCH. 223 (2004) (developing the concept of ethical fading, in which the moral dimensions of a decision gradually recede from awareness through self-deception and contextual framing, enabling individuals to engage in conduct they would otherwise recognize as unethical).

⁶² *See generally* Donald C. Langevoort, *Monitoring: The Behavioral Economics of Inducing Agents’ Compliance with Legal Rules* (Georgetown Univ. L. Ctr., Working Paper No. 276121, 2001) (examining how structural features of corporate organizations, including divergent

this perspective, voluntary compliance regimes risk creating perverse incentives: firms most capable of exploiting trust are often those best positioned to appear trustworthy *ex ante*.

The skeptical implication is clear: in the absence of robust external discipline, corporations may systematically instrumentalize trust. Unlike individuals, who may experience guilt or reputational shame within close social networks, corporations lack internal moral brakes. Trust, without verification, may therefore invite opportunism rather than cooperation.

C. Behavioral Ethics and Corporate “Good People”

The challenge of corporate voluntary compliance is compounded by insights from behavioral ethics research. In *The Law of Good People*, I argue that much legal and regulatory analysis implicitly assumes a sharp distinction between “good” people who comply with laws for ethical reasons and “bad” people who knowingly violate laws for personal gain.⁶³ This binary model underlies deterrence-based approaches, which assumes that raising the expected costs of violation causes rational calculators to choose compliance. But the binary model fails to account for a large category of behavior: wrongdoing by otherwise ethical people who do not recognize the full moral or legal significance of their conduct. This category of behavior poses distinctive

incentive structures, competitive pressures, and internal information silos, create compliance challenges that operate independently of individual employees' personal ethics, and arguing that attention to organizational norms and culture may produce better compliance outcomes than aggressive command-and-control monitoring).

⁶³ See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 1–30 ((challenging the binary model of compliance that divides regulated actors into rational bad actors deterred by sanctions and law-abiding good actors who comply for moral reasons, and arguing that a large category of legally significant behavior falls between these poles, driven by cognitive biases, self-serving rationalizations, and situational pressures that lead otherwise ethical individuals to engage in misconduct without recognizing its ethical dimensions)).

regulatory challenges that neither pure deterrence nor pure trust-based approaches adequately address.

Behavioral ethics research has documented numerous psychological mechanisms that allow “good people” to engage in unethical behavior while maintaining their self-image as ethical actors. These include ethical fading, where the moral dimensions of a decision become obscured by other considerations, motivated reasoning—where people interpret ambiguous information in self-serving ways—, and the what-the-hell effect—where small initial transgressions pave the way for larger ones.⁶⁴ The disparity between perceived and actual motivations raises serious concerns about the reliability of voluntary compliance, especially under conditions of limited monitoring.⁶⁵ Due to the lack of robust empirical evidence on the long-term sustainability of intrinsically motivated compliance in the face of conflicting interests, there is a risk that policies overly reliant on voluntary compliance may ultimately prove ineffective or even counterproductive.

These dynamics may be amplified in corporate contexts. In *Corporate Law for Good People*, written with Adi Libson and Gideon Parchomovsky, we examined how organizational structures and incentives can systematically promote unethical behavior among employees who would act ethically in their personal lives.⁶⁶ Several features of corporate environments

⁶⁴ See Tenbrunsel & Messick, *supra* note 44, at 225, 233; Peter H. Ditto, David A. Pizarro & David Tannenbaum, *Motivated Moral Reasoning*, 50 PSYCH. LEARNING & MOTIVATION 307, 312–13 (2009).

⁶⁵ See MAX H. BAZERMAN & ANN E. TENBRUNSEL, BLIND SPOTS: WHY WE FAIL TO DO WHAT’S RIGHT AND WHAT TO DO ABOUT IT 6 (2011) (documenting systematic gaps between individuals’ ethical self-perceptions and their actual behavior, and arguing that people consistently overestimate their capacity for ethical conduct while remaining unaware of the situational and psychological forces that lead them to act contrary to their stated values).

⁶⁶ See Feldman, Libson & Parchomovsky, *supra* note 9, at 1125.

contribute to this effect, creating conditions under which behavioral ethics concerns are particularly acute.

First, the diffusion of responsibility in corporate hierarchies can lead employees to view themselves as mere instruments of organizational decisions rather than moral agents making ethical choices.⁶⁷ When decisions are made collectively and implemented through chains of command, it becomes psychologically easier for individuals to disclaim responsibility for outcomes they would never choose personally. The psychological distance between corporate decision-makers and the consequences of their decisions exacerbates this dynamic.⁶⁸ A manager who would never personally harm a consumer may have little difficulty approving a policy that harms consumers at a distance. Thompson and Loewenstein have shown that people are more likely to remember information that aligns with their own position. This selective recall results in biased judgments of what is fair that align with their interest in outcomes..⁶⁹ The fact that these biases operate without awareness makes it difficult for people to notice the process of ethical erosion.

Second, competitive pressures and performance incentives create environments where employees feel compelled to cut ethical corners to meet targets. When compensation and career advancement depend on achieving aggressive performance goals, employees may engage in conduct they know to be problematic while rationalizing that “everyone does it” or that the

⁶⁷ *See id.* at 1145–49.

⁶⁸ *See* Don A. Moore & George Loewenstein, *Self-Interest, Automaticity, and the Psychology of Conflict of Interest*, 17 *SOC. JUST. RSCH.* 189, 196–97 (2004).

⁶⁹ *See* Leigh Thompson & George Loewenstein, *Egocentric Interpretations of Fairness and Interpersonal Conflict*, 51 *ORG. BEHAV. & HUM. DECISION PROCESSES* 176, 180 (1992) (“Individuals involved in a dispute may distort the facts of the case or the significance of those facts in a manner that favors their own position.”).

company implicitly expects such behavior.⁷⁰ Research on toxic corporate cultures has documented how organizational norms can override individual ethical commitments, creating systematic patterns of deviance⁷¹. Moore and Loewenstein were among the first to show that self-interest and concern for others affect behavior through different cognitive systems, and that self-interest, unlike concern for others, is automatic, viscerally compelling, and often unconscious.⁷²

Third, corporate environments often involve repeated interactions with ambiguous ethical dimensions, precisely the conditions under which behavioral ethics research suggests that ethical sensitivity erodes.⁷³ An employee who initially feels uncomfortable with aggressive accounting practices may, after repeated exposure, come to view such practices as normal and acceptable. The gradual normalization of questionable conduct can transform organizations into what I have called “hotbeds for unethicity,”⁷⁴ where individually ethical employees collectively produce

⁷⁰ See van Rooij & Fine, *supra* note 58, at 30; Langevoort, *supra* note 53, at 15.

⁷¹ See *id.*, at 10-15 (documenting how organizational norms and reward structures can override individual employees' ethical commitments, producing systematic deviance that persists even when individual actors are replaced); see also Benjamin van Rooij & Adam Fine, *The Behavioral Code: The Hidden Ways the Law Makes Us Better ... or Worse* (2021) (developing a broader account of how organizational environments shape individual compliance behavior, showing that corporate misconduct is better understood as a product of systemic organizational dynamics than of individual moral failure).

⁷² See Don A. Moore, Lloyd Tanlu & Max H. Bazerman, *Conflict of Interest and the Intrusion of Bias*, 5 JUDGMENT & DECISION MAKING 37, 38 (2010).

⁷³ See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 44, at 32–57 (analyzing how repeated exposure to ethically ambiguous situations gradually erodes individuals' sensitivity to the moral dimensions of their conduct, a process that is particularly pronounced in organizational settings where routine practices normalize borderline behavior and where the incremental nature of ethical erosion makes it difficult for actors to recognize the cumulative drift from their own ethical standards).

⁷⁴ See Feldman, Yuval. "1-Introduction: Can the Public Be Trusted?." (2025).

unethical outcomes.⁷⁵ This gradual erosion of ethical sensitivity poses particular challenges for voluntary compliance frameworks, which assumes that regulated parties can recognize and respond to the ethical dimensions of their conduct.

The research base supporting these concerns is substantial. Studies have demonstrated that people truly believe their own biased judgments, not recognizing any problems in their responses.⁷⁶ There is growing recognition that many ethical decisions result from implicit, not explicit choices.⁷⁷ Given that people's unethical behavior is frequently accompanied by, or the result of, a limited and distorted view of their own conduct, it is particularly important to focus on legal violations by otherwise good actors in the corporate context.⁷⁸ In the employer-employee relationship, issues such as ambiguity, repeated smaller violations, and the strong effect of workplace norms are likely to have a significant impact on conduct.⁷⁹

D. Structural Impediments to Intrinsic Motivation

Beyond the general challenges of corporate instrumentalism and behavioral ethics, several structural features of modern corporations specifically impede the development of intrinsic compliance motivation. These structural impediments operate independently of individual

⁷⁵ See Feldman, Libson & Parchomovsky, *supra* note 9, at 1125.

⁷⁶ See e.g., Nicholas Epley & Eugene M. Caruso, *Egocentric Ethics*, 17 SOC. JUST. RSCH. 171, 173 (2004) ((demonstrating that individuals' ethical judgments are systematically biased in self-serving directions, and that people are genuinely unaware of these biases, sincerely believing their skewed assessments to be objective and fair).

⁷⁷ See Nina Mazar, On Amir & Dan Ariely, *The Dishonesty of Honest People: A Theory of Self-Concept Maintenance*, 45 J. MKTG. RSCH. 633, 633 (2008).

⁷⁸ See David M. Bersoff, *Why Good People Sometimes Do Bad Things: Motivated Reasoning and Unethical Behavior*, 25 PERSONALITY & SOC. PSYCH. BULL. 28, 29 (1999).

⁷⁹ See Yuval Feldman, Benjamin van Rooij & Melissa Rorie, *Rule-Breaking Without Crime: Insights from Behavioral Ethics for the Study of Everyday Deviancy*, 44 CRIMINOLOGIST 8, 8 (2019).

psychology, creating systematic pressures toward instrumental compliance regardless of the personal ethics of corporate decision-makers⁸⁰.

The first structural impediment is the separation of ownership and control. In publicly traded corporations, the individuals making compliance decisions, managers and employees, are not the same individuals who bear the primary financial consequences of those decisions, which are the shareholders.⁸¹ This separation creates agency problems that may undermine voluntary compliance. Managers may engage in misconduct to advance their own careers or to meet performance targets even when such conduct is not in shareholders' long-term interests. Conversely, managers may avoid beneficial compliance investments because the costs are immediate and visible while the benefits are diffuse and long-term.⁸² The agency problem is

⁸⁰ See John C. Coffee, Jr., *"No Soul to Damn: No Body to Kick": An Unscandalized Inquiry into the Problem of Corporate Punishment*, 79 Mich. L. Rev. 386, 389-93 (1981) (arguing that the structural characteristics of corporations, including diffused decision-making, separation of ownership and control, and information asymmetries, create compliance incentive problems that cannot be solved by appealing to the personal ethics of individual managers); see also Feldman, Libson & Parchomovsky, *supra* note 9, at 1136-40 (identifying organizational structure, rather than individual moral character, as the primary driver of corporate misconduct, and arguing that regulatory design must account for the ways that corporate architecture systematically channels individual behavior toward instrumental compliance).

⁸¹ See Adolf A. Berle & Gardiner C. Means, *The Modern Corporation and Private Property* 112-16 (1933); see also Ronald J. Gilson & Jeffrey N. Gordon, *The Agency Costs of Agency Capitalism: Activist Investors and the Revaluation of Governance Rights*, 113 Colum. L. Rev. 863, 865-74 (2013) (updating the Berle and Means thesis to account for the rise of institutional investors as intermediaries between individual shareholders and corporate managers, arguing that this layered separation further attenuates the link between those who bear the financial consequences of corporate decisions and those who make them).

⁸² See Michael C. Jensen & William H. Meckling, *Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure*, 3 J. FIN. ECON. 305, 313 (1976) ((defining agency costs as the sum of monitoring expenditures, bonding costs, and residual loss arising from the divergence of interests between principals and agents, and demonstrating that managers bearing the full cost of compliance investments but capturing only a fraction of the resulting benefits will systematically underinvest in value-enhancing activities whose returns accrue primarily to shareholders).).

particularly acute for compliance decisions, which often involve trading off short-term costs (compliance investments) against long-term benefits (reduced liability, enhanced reputation) in ways that are difficult for shareholders to observe and evaluate.

The second structural impediment is the complexity and opacity of corporate compliance obligations. Modern corporations operate under dense webs of regulatory requirements spanning multiple jurisdictions and subject areas. The sheer volume and complexity of these requirements can produce what Yotam Kaplan and I have termed “ethical blind spots,” which are situations where violations occur not because of deliberate evasion, but because the legal requirements are genuinely unclear or unknown to decision-makers.⁸³ When compliance is uncertain, the conditions for developing intrinsic motivation to comply are undermined; people cannot internalize commitments to requirements they do not understand.

The third structural impediment is the increasing use of technology in both corporate operations and regulatory enforcement. As I discuss in *Can the Public Be Trusted?*, technological advances enable more comprehensive monitoring and enforcement, but they may simultaneously crowd out intrinsic compliance motivation.⁸⁴ When corporations know that their conduct is being continuously monitored, any compliance they exhibit becomes attributable to

⁸³ See Yuval Feldman & Yotam Kaplan, *Ethical Blind Spots & Regulatory Traps: On Distorted Regulatory Incentives, Behavioral Ethics & Legal Design*, in L. & ECON. REGUL. 37, 37–39 (Klaus Mathis & Avishalom Tor eds., 2021).

⁸⁴ See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 165–185 (See generally Feldman, *supra* note 3, at 165–85 (examining how advances in regulatory technology expand the state's capacity to monitor and enforce compliance, while documenting the risk that pervasive technological monitoring crowds out the intrinsic motivation that voluntary compliance depends upon).).

the monitoring rather than to internal commitment. Paradoxically, technological improvements in enforcement capacity may undermine the conditions necessary for trust-based regulation.⁸⁵

E. The Problem of Self-Regulation and Public Trust

A related challenge for corporate voluntary compliance is the relationship between self-regulation and public trust. Research conducted with David Levi-Faur and Libby Maman examined how public trust is affected by various forms of regulation, comparing state regulation with enhanced forms of self-regulation.⁸⁶ The findings reveal important limitations on trust-based corporate approaches.

Our research showed that public trust in regulated firms increases when state regulation exists, while self-regulation, even if enhanced, leads to lower levels of public trust.⁸⁷ All forms of self-regulation are less trusted by the public than a state regulatory regime. The interaction effects we found suggest that governments play an important role in ensuring public trust in the market.⁸⁸ This is true not only with governments as regulators, but also when combining self-

⁸⁵ See generally *id.* at 165–185 (See generally *id.* at 165-85 (arguing that the paradox of technology-enhanced enforcement is that it may erode the trust relationship between regulators and regulated parties, as continuous surveillance signals distrust and causes regulated actors to attribute their own compliance to external pressure rather than internal commitment)).

⁸⁶ See Libby Maman, Yuval Feldman & David Levi-Faur, *Varieties of Regulatory Regimes and Their Effect on Citizens' Trust in Firms*, 30 J. EUR. PUB. POL'Y 2807, 2807–09 (2023).

⁸⁷ See *id.* at 2815-18 (finding that public trust in regulated firms is significantly higher under state regulation than under any form of self-regulation, including enhanced self-regulatory designs, and that even the addition of sanctioning mechanisms to self-regulatory regimes does not bring public trust levels to those achieved by direct state oversight).

⁸⁸ See *id.* at 2819-22 (reporting significant interaction effects between state involvement and self-regulatory design, showing that government participation in regulatory regimes enhances public trust not only through direct state regulation but also when state oversight is combined with self-regulatory instruments such as pledges, and that the effectiveness of self-regulation in generating trust is contingent on citizens' baseline trust in government).

regulatory instruments such as pledges. The findings demonstrated that more government regulation leads to more trust, while trust in self-regulation depends on the public's baseline trust in the government.⁸⁹

Within self-regulatory designs, we find that self-regulatory constellations that include the possibility of sanctioning generate higher trust than those without sanction mechanisms.⁹⁰ This finding suggests that even when regulators adopt trust-based approaches, they cannot entirely abandon enforcement capacity without undermining public confidence in the regulatory system. The public appears to require some assurance that violations will be detected and punished, even in a predominantly trust-based regime.

Taken together, these considerations present a sobering picture for corporate voluntary compliance. The instrumental orientation of corporate decision-making, the behavioral ethics challenges of organizational contexts, the structural impediments to intrinsic motivation, and the public trust challenges of self-regulation all suggest that trust-based regulatory approaches may be less effective with corporations than with individuals. Yet, the picture is not solely pessimistic.

⁸⁹ *See id.* at 2822-24 (finding that the relationship between regulatory design and public trust is moderated by citizens' pre-existing trust in government, such that self-regulatory regimes generate meaningful trust only where baseline governmental trust is already high, while state regulation produces higher trust levels regardless of baseline attitudes toward government).

⁹⁰ *See id.* at 2822-18. (we did find that the possibility of sanctions in case of violations (civil enforcement) increases trust compared with self-regulation without sanctions)

IV. THE HOPEFUL CASE: CONDITIONS FOR CORPORATE VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE

A. Reputational Sensitivity and Repeat-Player Dynamics

While the previous part cataloged reasons for skepticism about corporate voluntary compliance, corporations possess certain characteristics that may make them more amenable to trust-based regulation than individuals. The most significant characteristic is corporate sensitivity to reputational consequences.

Corporations, particularly publicly traded ones, depend critically on their reputations with consumers, investors, employees, and regulators. Reputational damage from compliance failures can dwarf formal legal sanctions in its impact on corporate value.⁹¹ The market capitalization loss from a major compliance scandal often exceeds any fines or penalties by orders of magnitude. This reputational sensitivity creates incentives for compliance that operate independently of the formal enforcement regime and can motivate compliance even when the probability of formal sanctions is low.

Crucially, reputational mechanisms can motivate beyond-compliance behavior that pure deterrence models cannot explain. A corporation concerned about its reputation may comply not merely with the letter of legal requirements, but also with normative ideals; it may adopt industry best practices that exceed legal minima, and proactively address potential compliance concerns before regulators identify them.⁹² This pattern resembles the beyond-compliance behavior that voluntary compliance theory attributes to intrinsic motivation, though the corporate motivation is

⁹¹ See John Armour, Colin Mayer & Andrea Polo, *Regulatory Sanctions and Reputational Damage in Financial Markets*, 52 J. FIN. & QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS 1429, 1429–30 (2017).

⁹² See Robert G. Eccles, Ioannis Ioannou & George Serafeim, *The Impact of Corporate Sustainability on Organizational Processes and Performance*, 60 MGMT. SCI. 2835, 2840 (2014).

ultimately instrumental (protecting reputation) rather than intrinsic (believing in the rightness of compliance). The functional equivalence suggests that reputational mechanisms may serve as a substitute for intrinsic motivation in the corporate context, achieving similar behavioral outcomes through different psychological pathways.

Shaming mechanisms in corporate law illustrate this dynamic. As David Skeel has argued, shaming can serve as a powerful compliance mechanism in corporate contexts, leveraging corporations' sensitivity to reputational harm.⁹³ Public disclosure of compliance failures, even without formal sanctions, can impose significant costs on corporations through effects on stock prices, customer relationships, and employee morale. This reputational sensitivity provides a lever for regulators to influence corporate behavior without relying exclusively on formal enforcement.

Related to reputational sensitivity is the repeat-player dynamic of corporate regulatory interactions. Most corporations of any significant size engage in ongoing relationships with regulatory authorities across multiple transactions and extended time periods.⁹⁴ This repeat-player status creates (extrinsic motivation) incentives for cooperative behavior that would not exist in one-shot interactions. A corporation that develops a reputation for trustworthiness with regulators may receive more favorable treatment, faster approvals, fewer audits, and more lenient interpretations of ambiguous requirements, which more than compensates for any gains from short-term evasion.⁷ The repeat-player dynamic creates conditions favorable to the emergence

⁹³ See David A. Skeel, Jr., *Shaming in Corporate Law*, 149 U. PA. L. REV. 1811, 1811-12 (2001).

⁹⁴ See Robert A. Kagan, Neil Gunningham & Dorothy Thornton, *Fear, Duty, and Regulatory Compliance: Lessons from Three Research Projects*, in EXPLAINING COMPLIANCE: BUSINESS RESPONSES TO REGULATION 37, 37-38 (Christine Parker & Vibeke Lehmann Nielsen eds., 2011).

of cooperative equilibria between regulators and regulated corporations, even in the absence of intrinsic compliance motivation.

B. Private Ordering and Community Governance

The literature on private ordering and self-regulation provides empirical support for these dynamics. Lisa Bernstein's studies of the diamond and cotton industries demonstrate how reputational mechanisms can support cooperation among commercial actors outside formal legal systems.⁹⁵ Barak Richman's work on Jewish diamond merchants shows how community-based reputation systems can substitute for and even outperform legal enforcement in generating trustworthy behavior.⁹⁶ The diamond industry is notable in that it relies heavily on reputation and social bonds at low cost, creating a system that enables many transactions to be completed entirely outside the formal legal system⁹⁷.

⁹⁵ See Lisa Bernstein, *Opting Out of the Legal System: Extralegal Contractual Relations in the Diamond Industry*, 21 *J. Legal Stud.* 115, 116-17 (1992) (documenting how diamond merchants in the New York diamond industry rely on trust, reputation, and extralegal enforcement mechanisms administered through industry associations and arbitration tribunals rather than formal legal institutions to govern complex commercial transactions, and arguing that this private ordering system succeeds because the close-knit structure of the industry makes reputational sanctions a credible and low-cost substitute for legal enforcement).

⁹⁶ See Barak D. Richman, *How Community Institutions Create Economic Advantage: Jewish Diamond Merchants in New York*, 31 *L. & SOC. INQUIRY* 383, 398 (2006) (discussing how credibility in diamond trading markets stems from merchants' affiliation with tightly connected communities in which identity and reputation support the enforcement of contractual promises).

⁹⁷ See Barak D. Richman, *Stateless Commerce: The Diamond Network and the Persistence of Relational Exchange* 35-42 (2017) (arguing that the diamond industry's ethnic trading networks persist because reputation and social bonds enforce commercial obligations at lower cost than formal legal institutions, and that modern courts are ill-equipped to adjudicate diamond disputes given the specialized expertise required for identification, measurement, and valuation, making community-based enforcement not merely a cultural preference but a functionally superior governance mechanism).

The cotton industry also created a type of self-regulatory private legal system to govern transactions among its members outside of the public legal system.⁹⁸ Robert Ellickson showed how social norms and considerations of efficiency led neighbors in Shasta County to cooperate beyond what was required by law.⁹⁹ In Shasta County, research reveals that law plays a lesser role than expected in neighborly relationships. People largely govern themselves using informal rules and social norms that develop without the aid of a state or other central coordinators. Mark Suchman's sociological study of lawyers in Silicon Valley presents an alternative view of the legal profession, describing it as engaging in the venture capital financing of new technology-based corporations. In this context, lawyers are viewed favorably by their clients and are perceived as adding value to a transaction rather than arguing over how to divide the transactional pie, a result of trust-based relationships.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁸ See Lisa Bernstein, *Private Commercial Law in the Cotton Industry: Creating Cooperation Through Rules, Norms, and Institutions*, 99 *Mich. L. Rev.* 1724, 1727-28 (2001) (documenting how the American cotton industry developed a comprehensive private legal system, administered through industry trade associations and merchant tribunals, that governs transactions among members through its own substantive rules, arbitration procedures, and reputational sanctions, largely displacing reliance on public courts and state-created commercial law).

⁹⁹ (See Robert C. Ellickson, *Order Without Law: How Neighbors Settle Disputes* 48, 64 (1991) (documenting how cattle ranchers and farmers in Shasta County, California resolved disputes over stray cattle and boundary fences through informal norms rather than formal legal rules, and finding that these norms tended toward efficient outcomes, suggesting that close-knit communities can generate cooperative behavior that exceeds legal requirements without state intervention).

¹⁰⁰ See Mark C. Suchman & Mia L. Cahill, *The Hired Gun as Facilitator: Lawyers and the Suppression of Business Disputes in Silicon Valley*, 21 *L. & Soc. Inquiry* 679, 680 (1996) (finding that lawyers in Silicon Valley's venture capital ecosystem function less as adversarial advocates and more as relationship facilitators who help structure transactions, suppress disputes before they escalate, and build trust between entrepreneurs and investors, resulting in clients who view legal counsel as adding value rather than imposing costs); see also Ronald J. Gilson, *Value Creation by Business Lawyers: Legal Skills and Asset Pricing*, 94 *Yale L.J.* 239, 243-48 (1984) (arguing that business lawyers create value by reducing transaction costs, bridging information asymmetries between parties, and engineering contractual structures that enable commercial

While many consider this “order without law” paradigm not easily translated to other spheres where reputation systems are not as effective, it does suggest the importance of accounting for community governance as a potential alternative to state command and control¹⁰¹. As demonstrated in discussions of environmental behavior, community governance can be used as an important alternative tool to state regulation and could help achieve voluntary compliance more effectively in contexts where ongoing relationships and reputational stakes are sufficiently high.

C. Bureaucratic Transparency, Data Richness, and Monitoring Compatibility

A second characteristic of corporations that may facilitate trust-based regulation is the bureaucratic transparency of their operations. Unlike individual conduct, which often occurs privately and leaves limited documentary traces, corporate conduct typically occurs through formal processes that generate extensive records.¹⁰² Corporations maintain accounting records, internal communications, meeting minutes, and compliance documentation that provide a rich evidentiary base for regulatory oversight¹⁰³. This documentation exists for business purposes

cooperation that would otherwise fail, a framework that recast the lawyer's role from adversarial cost center to productive participant in value-creating transactions).

¹⁰¹ See Robert C. Ellickson, *Order Without Law: How Neighbors Settle Disputes* 48, 64 (1991)

¹⁰² The classical argument is of course of MAX WEBER, *ECONOMY AND SOCIETY: AN OUTLINE OF INTERPRETIVE SOCIOLOGY* 957 (Guenther Roth & Clause Wittich eds., 1978) (describing rational-legal bureaucracy as a hierarchical system of rules and procedures that minimizes arbitrary decision-making and thereby supports consistent compliance with formal legal norm). For a more recent and concrete argument, see Shannon P. Carcelli, *Bureaucratic Structure and Compliance with International Agreements*, 68 AM. J. POL. SCI. 177, 178–82 (2024) (arguing that a well-structured domestic bureaucracy can encourage compliance with international agreements by empowering bureaucrats whose careers and reputations depend on compliance and by aligning institutional incentives toward faithful implementation).

¹⁰³ See John Armour, Jeffrey N. Gordon & Geeyoung Min, *Taking Compliance Seriously*, 37 Yale J. on Reg. 1, 14-18 (2020) (describing the compliance infrastructure of modern

independent of regulatory requirements, meaning that regulators can often verify compliance without imposing additional monitoring burdens.

In ongoing work with Ori Aronson and Orly Lobel on behavioral recognition technology and predictive trust, we develop this distinction more systematically.¹⁰⁴ Our analysis suggests that corporate and individual trust assessment differ in important ways which may support focusing initial applications of algorithmic trust systems with business regulation¹⁰⁵. Corporations have formal compliance systems, organizational continuity, and more data points tracking their interactions with the various regulatory bodies than individuals possess.¹⁰⁶ These characteristics

corporations, including internal reporting systems, record-keeping obligations, and documentation requirements that generate continuous evidentiary records of corporate conduct available to regulators); *see also* Geoffrey Parsons Miller, *The Compliance Function: An Overview*, in *The Oxford Handbook of Corporate Law and Governance* 981, 988-93 (Jeffrey N. Gordon & Wolf-Georg Ringe eds., 2018) (*detailing how corporate compliance programs produce systematic documentation, including audit trails, internal investigation reports, training records, and communications logs, that serve both internal governance and external regulatory oversight functions*).

¹⁰⁴ [See Ori Aronson, Yuval Feldman & Orly Lobel, Behavioral Recognition Technology: forthcoming Indiana Law Journal 2026](#)

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=6427698 (). This analysis demonstrates that corporations present fundamentally different trust assessment challenges than individuals: corporations have formal compliance systems, organizational continuity, far more data points tracking their interactions with various regulatory bodies, and fewer privacy expectations. These characteristics make corporations better testing grounds for sophisticated trust technologies. The “corporations first” principle reflects both practical and legal considerations, agencies should focus on corporate applications across domains before extending algorithmic trust assessment to individuals, where privacy, dignity, and constitutional concerns loom larger.

¹⁰⁵ *See id.* ((ssrn) manuscript at 15-20) (arguing that corporations' formal organizational structures, data-rich regulatory interactions, and reduced privacy expectations make them preferable initial subjects for algorithmic trust assessment systems, and proposing a "corporations first" principle for deploying predictive regulatory technologies).

¹⁰⁶ *See id.* (manuscript at 20-25) (documenting the data advantages corporations present for trust assessment, including formal compliance records, auditable internal controls, organizational continuity across personnel changes, and multi-agency regulatory histories that collectively

make corporations better testing grounds for sophisticated trust technologies. Crucially, corporations also face fewer privacy expectations and constitutional complications than individuals¹⁰⁷. When agencies employ algorithms to assess individual trustworthiness based on past compliance behavior, concerns arise regarding harm to human rights and the dignity of people, what we term the risks of “profiling” individuals¹⁰⁸. These concerns are substantially attenuated in the corporate context, allowing regulators to focus on institutional learning while minimizing risks to fundamental rights.

This bureaucratic transparency and data richness have important implications for voluntary compliance frameworks. One concern with trust-based regulation is that reducing monitoring and enforcement allows undetected violations to flourish¹⁰⁹. But corporate transparency means that reduced formal enforcement need not equate to reduced visibility of

provide far richer inputs for algorithmic prediction than the data available for individual regulated parties).

¹⁰⁷ *See id.* (manuscript at 25-30) (contrasting the constitutional and normative constraints on algorithmic assessment of individuals, including privacy rights, dignity concerns, and the risk of profiling, with the substantially attenuated constraints applicable to corporations, which lack constitutionally protected dignity interests and face weaker claims against regulatory differentiation based on behavioral history).

¹⁰⁸ *See* Aronson, Feldman & Lobel, *supra* note 104 (manuscript at 30-35) (developing the concept of “behavioral recognition technology” and arguing that algorithmic assessment of individual compliance behavior raises profiling concerns analogous to those identified in criminal justice contexts, including risks to privacy, dignity, and equal treatment); *see also* Solon Barocas & Andrew D. Selbst, *Big Data's Disparate Impact*, 104 Cal. L. Rev. 671, 688-93 (2016) (documenting how algorithmic decision-making systems can reproduce and amplify existing biases, raising particular concerns when applied to individuals whose fundamental rights may be at stake).

¹⁰⁹ *See* Feldman, *supra* note 3, at 257-8 (identifying the risk that trust-based regulatory approaches may create opportunities for undetected noncompliance, particularly where monitoring is relaxed without adequate substitute mechanisms for verifying continued adherence to regulatory requirements).

corporate conduct¹¹⁰. Regulators can maintain awareness of corporate conduct through disclosure requirements, periodic audits, and third-party monitoring without engaging in the intensive enforcement that may crowd out intrinsic compliance motivation¹¹¹.

Moreover, corporate transparency facilitates the differentiated regulatory treatment that our work on “predictive trust” explores.¹¹² With individuals, using past behavior to inform future regulatory treatment raises significant concerns about privacy, dignity, and autonomy.¹¹³ With corporations, these concerns are substantially attenuated. Corporations do not have dignity interests in the same sense that individuals do; regulatory treatment based on past compliance history does not violate corporate privacy or autonomy in constitutionally significant ways.¹¹⁴ This asymmetry means that regulators can more freely employ data-driven, behavior-based

¹¹⁰ *See id.* at 183-184 (arguing that the data richness of corporate operations provides regulators with alternative channels for verifying compliance that do not depend on intensive direct enforcement, including mandatory disclosures, financial reporting obligations, and third-party certification systems).

¹¹¹ *See* Jodi L. Short & Michael W. Toffel, *Making Self-Regulation More Than Merely Symbolic: The Critical Role of the Legal Environment*, 55 *Admin. Sci. Q.* 361, 365-70 (2010) (finding that third-party auditing and disclosure requirements function as effective compliance verification mechanisms that allow regulators to maintain oversight without the adversarial enforcement interactions that may undermine cooperative regulatory relationships); *see also* Feldman, *supra* note 3, at 183-84, 258 (discussing how periodic audits and disclosure-based monitoring can preserve the informational benefits of enforcement while avoiding the motivational crowding-out effects associated with continuous surveillance).

¹¹² *See* FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 170-173.

¹¹³ *See id.* at 166–67 (*See id.* at 166-67 (discussing how using personalized data on individuals' past behavior to inform regulatory treatment raises concerns about undermining personal autonomy and freedom of choice, and arguing that the comparison between trust-based and technology-based regulatory approaches should focus on which is more detrimental to individuals' ability to decide whether to comply with state laws and regulations).).

¹¹⁴ Feldman, Yuval, CAN CORPORATIONS BE TRUSTED? VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE AND THE LIMITS OF NON-COERCIVE BUSINESS REGULATION (February 03, 2026). Bar Ilan University Faculty of Law Research Paper No. 6174323, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=6174323> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6174323>

differentiation with corporations, directing trust-based approaches toward corporations with strong compliance histories while concentrating enforcement resources on corporations with poor compliance records. The “corporations first” principle thus reflects both practical considerations, better data, more testing grounds, and legal ones, fewer constitutional complications.¹¹⁵

D. Existing Voluntary & trust based Compliance Programs

Overview: Evidence from Existing Trust-Based Programs

Perhaps, some of the strongest evidence for the viability of corporate voluntary compliance comes from studies of existing programs that embody trust-based principles. Several U.S. administrative agencies have developed audit-based voluntary compliance programs that offer corporations enhanced guidance and reduced penalties in exchange for cooperative compliance approaches, though their effectiveness appears to depend on supportive enforcement conditions and does not fully replace traditional deterrence-based mechanisms.¹¹⁶ These programs

¹¹⁵ *See id* at 20.

¹¹⁶ *See generally* Jodi L. Short & Michael W. Toffel, *Making Self-Regulation More Than Merely Symbolic: The Critical Role of the Legal Environment*, 55 *Admin. Sci. Q.* 361, 365-70 (2010) (documenting how regulatory agencies have developed cooperative compliance programs that combine voluntary participation with credible enforcement capacity, and finding that such programs are most effective when embedded within a broader regulatory environment that maintains meaningful oversight); Ian Ayres & John Braithwaite, *Responsive Regulation: Transcending the Deregulation Debate* 4, 35-38 (1992) (providing the theoretical foundation for differentiated enforcement regimes in which regulators reserve cooperative approaches for entities that demonstrate trustworthiness while maintaining escalating sanctions for those that do not).

demonstrate that trust-based approaches can work with corporations under appropriate conditions¹¹⁷.

One such program is the Environmental Protection Agency’s (“EPA”) Audit Policy Program (“APP”). It allows companies to voluntarily disclose environmental violations in exchange for reduced penalties.¹¹⁸ Since its inception, the program has led to the discovery and correction of violations at thousands of facilities. Companies that participate in the program not only avoid the penalties they would otherwise face, but also benefit from the guidance and support that the EPA provides to help them achieve compliance. The program creates a cooperative dynamic in which regulators and regulated parties work together toward shared compliance objectives rather than engaging in adversarial enforcement interactions¹¹⁹.

The Internal Revenue Service’s (“IRS”) Compliance Assurance Process (“CAP”) provides another example. Under CAP, large corporate taxpayers pledge to maintain transparency about their tax positions in exchange for real-time guidance from IRS officials.¹²⁰ Research has shown

¹¹⁷ See *infra* Part IV.D.2 (examining in detail the EPA Audit Policy, the IRS Compliance Assurance Process, the SEC Cooperation Program, the FDA Voluntary Qualified Importer Program, Customs-Trade Partnership Against Terrorism, OSHA Voluntary Protection Program, and federal banking risk-based examination systems as concrete illustrations of trust-based corporate regulation across diverse regulatory domains).

¹¹⁸ Jodi L. Short & Michael W. Toffel, *Coerced Confessions: Self-Policing in the Shadow of the Regulator*, 24 J.L. ECONS. & ORG. 45, 49 (2008).

¹¹⁹ See Michael W. Toffel & Jodi L. Short, *Coming Clean and Cleaning Up: Does Voluntary Self-Reporting Indicate Effective Self-Policing?*, 54 J.L. & Econ. 609, 611-14, 630-35 (2011) (analyzing facility-level data showing that voluntary self-disclosure under the EPA Audit Policy led to reduced subsequent inspections, higher rates of clean inspections, and fewer abnormal releases, suggesting that the program fosters a cooperative compliance dynamic rather than an adversarial one).

¹²⁰ See Paul J. Beck & Petro Lisowsky, *Tax Uncertainty and Voluntary Real-Time Tax Audits*, 89 ACCT. REV. 867, 868 (2014).

that CAP participation decreases tax uncertainty, as measured by the reserves companies set aside for potential tax authority challenges.¹²¹ The program represents a shift from adversarial post-filing audits to cooperative real-time tax guidance, embodying the trust-based approach that responsive regulation theory advocates. However, finding the proper balance between trust and monitoring presents a significant challenge.

The Food and Drug Administration’s (“FDA”) Voluntary Qualified Importer Program (“VQIP”) uses trust-based certification to expedite food imports for international companies with strong safety records.¹²² Companies that demonstrate reliable compliance histories receive expedited review of their imports, reducing delays and costs.¹²³ The program creates incentives for companies to invest in compliance beyond minimum requirements to qualify for preferential treatment.

The Securities and Exchange Commission’s (“SEC”) 2010 cooperation program offers leniency for self-reporting securities violations.¹²⁴ Research by Andrew Leone, Edward Li, and Michelle Liu found that the program improved the effectiveness of securities enforcement by encouraging companies to come forward with violations they might otherwise have concealed.¹²⁵ The program demonstrates how trust-based approaches can complement, rather than replace

¹²¹ *See id.* at 898.

¹²² *See* Neal Fortin, *The U.S. Food Safety Modernization Act: Implications in Transnational Governance of Food Safety, Food System Sustainability, and the Tension with Free Trade*, 25 DUKE ENV’T. L. & POL’Y F. 313, 326 (2015).

¹²³ *See id.* 321-326.

¹²⁴ *See* Andrew J. Leone, Edward Xuejun Li & Michelle Liu, *On the SEC’s 2010 Enforcement Cooperation Program*, 71(1) J. ACCT. & ECON., Feb. 2021, at 1, 3.

¹²⁵ *See id.* at 19.

enforcement, using the promise of leniency to generate information that enhances the overall effectiveness of the regulatory regime¹²⁶.

This evidence suggests that when properly structured, corporate trust-based regulatory tools can achieve both instrumental goals (reducing enforcement costs) and normative ones (fostering cooperation and compliance culture).¹²⁷ The success of these programs does not prove that voluntary compliance will work in all corporate contexts, but it demonstrates that the approach is viable under appropriate conditions. While these programs demonstrate the viability of trust-based approaches, a deeper examination reveals the sophisticated institutional architecture underlying contemporary personalized corporate regulation. The following sections examine the doctrinal framework and operational mechanics of these personalized regulatory regimes in detail.

The IRS has developed the most sophisticated framework for personalized corporate tax compliance¹²⁸. The CAP, established in 2005, represents a fundamental departure from

¹²⁶ *See id.* at 17-19 (finding that the SEC's cooperation program increased both the quantity and quality of self-reported violations, enabling the SEC to detect misconduct it would not otherwise have uncovered and to resolve enforcement actions more efficiently); *see also* Brandon L. Garrett, *Too Big to Jail: How Prosecutors Compromise with Corporations* 60-65 (2014) (analyzing how deferred prosecution agreements and cooperation credit regimes function as information-generating mechanisms that extend the reach of enforcement agencies beyond what direct investigation could achieve, effectively enlisting regulated entities as participants in the enforcement process).

¹²⁷ *See generally* Jodi L. Short, *The Paranoid Style in Regulatory Reform*, 63 HASTINGS L.J. 633 (2012) ((arguing that regulatory reform discourse is driven less by efficiency concerns than by anxiety about state coercion, and that this framing helps explain the prominence of self-regulatory approaches as ostensibly non-coercive alternatives)).

¹²⁸ *See* Dennis de Widt, Emer Mulligan & Lynne Oats, *The US Compliance Assurance Process: A Relational Signalling Perspective*, 5 J. Tax Admin. 145, 146-48 (2019) (describing the US CAP as one of the pioneering cooperative compliance programs globally and analyzing its evolution from a pilot program to a comprehensive framework for real-time, trust-based

traditional post-filing audit models.¹²⁹ Under CAP, large corporate taxpayers with more transparent tax practices may receive earlier real-time resolution of tax issues before filing returns, reducing the uncertainty and cost associated with traditional audits, particularly for firms with moderate levels of tax uncertainty¹³⁰. Participation requires corporations to demonstrate strong internal controls, maintain complete transparency regarding tax positions, and disclose all material issues on a contemporaneous basis before filing.¹³¹

The program explicitly differentiates corporations based on past behavior. Admission to the program requires a history of substantial compliance and transparency¹³². The IRS evaluates applicants based on prior examination history, the quality of tax accrual processes, their relationship with IRS personnel, and their demonstrated willingness to work collaboratively.¹³³

engagement between the IRS and large corporate taxpayers); *see also* OECD, Co-operative Tax Compliance: Building Better Tax Control Frameworks 15-20 (2016) (identifying cooperative compliance programs, including the US CAP, as representing a fundamental shift in tax administration from adversarial post-filing audits toward collaborative pre-filing engagement, and providing comparative analysis of program design across jurisdictions).

¹²⁹ *See Compliance Assurance Process*, IRS (Aug. 22, 2025), <https://www.irs.gov/businesses/corporations/compliance-assurance-process> [<https://perma.cc/RD3F-J388>].

¹³⁰ *See Beck & Lisowsky, supra* note 88, at 868-72 (describing how CAP shifts the IRS's engagement with large corporate taxpayers from adversarial post-filing audits to cooperative pre-filing review, in which tax positions are identified and resolved in real time before returns are filed, substantially reducing the uncertainty costs that both taxpayers and the IRS incur under traditional examination processes).

¹³¹ *See CAP Memorandum of Understanding from the I.R.S. to Taxpayer* (Dec. 2020), <https://www.irs.gov/pub/irs-lbi/2021-cap-mou-final-12-2020.pdf> [<https://perma.cc/AC56-NUGL>].

¹³² *See Loren M. Opper, Compliance Assurance Process*, 63 *Tax Exec.* 413, 415-16 (2011) (describing the admission criteria for CAP, including a demonstrated history of substantial compliance, transparent tax reporting, and a cooperative relationship with IRS examination personnel).

¹³³ *See id* at 413, 418 (2011).

Once accepted, participants receive annual reviews¹³⁴. Poor performance or lack of transparency triggers removal from the program and reversion to traditional examination processes¹³⁵. This creates strong incentives for sustained cooperative behavior.¹³⁶

Empirical evidence demonstrates CAP effectiveness. Participating corporations show substantial reductions in tax reserves for uncertain positions, indicating genuine decrease in tax controversy rather than mere audit avoidance.¹³⁷ The program reduces IRS examination costs while improving compliance quality through early identification and resolution of issues¹³⁸. Since becoming permanent in 2011, CAP has enrolled a significant number of the largest U.S. corporate taxpayers, and the IRS expanded eligibility for the program beginning with the 2020 CAP year after a five-year pause on new admissions¹³⁹.

¹³⁴ See CAP Memorandum of Understanding, *supra* note 95, at 3-4 (establishing the annual review cycle under which the IRS evaluates each participant's continued eligibility based on ongoing transparency, the quality of internal controls, and the timely disclosure of material tax positions).

¹³⁵ See IRM § 4.51.8.3.1 (Aug. 7, 2025) (listing behaviors that disqualify applicants or trigger removal from CAP, including failure to maintain transparency, material misrepresentation of tax positions, and lack of cooperation with IRS personnel during the review process).

¹³⁶ See IRM § 4.51.8.3.1 (Aug. 7, 2025) (listing out various behaviors that would prohibit an applicant from participating in the program).

¹³⁷ See Beck & Lisowsky, *supra* note 82, at 898.

¹³⁸ See de Widt, Mulligan & Oats, *infra* note 99, at 150-53 (finding that CAP reduces examination costs for both the IRS and participating taxpayers by shifting the resolution of disputed tax positions from resource-intensive post-filing audits to collaborative pre-filing review, and that this early engagement improves the quality of compliance by identifying and addressing potential issues before they harden into adversarial disputes).

¹³⁹ See *Compliance Assurance Process*, IRS (Aug. 22, 2025), <https://www.irs.gov/businesses/corporations/compliance-assurance-process> [<https://perma.cc/RD3F-J388>] (documenting CAP's evolution from a pilot program in 2005 to a permanent program in 2011, the suspension of new applications from 2015 to 2019, and the reopening and expansion of the program beginning with the 2020 CAP year); see also de Widt,

The IRS also employs behavioral recognition in its broader enforcement strategy. The Return Review Program uses machine learning algorithms to analyze patterns in corporate tax filings, assigning risk scores based on deviations from expected patterns, historical compliance behavior, and network connections to high-risk entities.¹⁴⁰ This algorithmic approach enables targeted examination of high-risk returns while expediting processing for low-risk filers. The system continuously updates as new filing data becomes available, creating dynamic trust assessments rather than static categorical judgments¹⁴¹.

The EPA Audit Policy, formally titled the Incentives for Self-Policing: Discovery, Disclosure, Correction and Prevention of Violations, established in 1995 and revised in 2000, creates explicit incentives for voluntary disclosure of environmental violations.¹⁴² The policy offers significant penalty reductions, and in many cases complete elimination of gravity-based civil penalties, for companies that voluntarily discover, promptly disclose, and expeditiously correct violations.¹⁴³

Mulligan & Oats, *supra* note 99, at 154 (reporting on the scope and operation of CAP prior to the 2020 expansion).

¹⁴⁰ See generally TAXPAYER ADVOCATE SERV., NATIONAL TAXPAYER ADVOCATE ANNUAL REPORT TO CONGRESS 35–36 (2019) (discussing the IRS’s use of algorithms in return selection).

¹⁴¹ See Cary Coglianese & David Lehr, *Regulating by Robot: Administrative Decision Making in the Machine-Learning Era*, 105 Geo. L.J. 1147, 1163-71 (2017) (describing how agencies use algorithmic and machine-learning tools to score cases by risk and target enforcement resources, including longstanding systems such as the IRS’s Discriminant Function System for selecting returns for audit)

¹⁴² Incentives for Self-Policing: Discovery, Disclosure, Correction and Prevention of Violations, 65 Fed. Reg. 19618, 19625 (Apr. 11, 2000).

¹⁴³ See *id.* at 19620.

This program distinguishes between entities based on behavioral patterns¹⁴⁴. To qualify for maximum penalty mitigation, companies must demonstrate systematic compliance efforts through environmental management systems or compliance-focused auditing programs.¹⁴⁵ Repeat violators, or entities with patterns of noncompliance, receive reduced benefits or complete exclusion from the policy¹⁴⁶. The EPA explicitly considers compliance history when determining penalty mitigation, creating graduated benefits tied to demonstrated trustworthiness.¹⁴⁷

Between 1995 and 2020, the Audit Policy resulted in over 28,000 facility disclosures covering more than 300,000 individual violations at facilities nationwide.¹⁴⁸ Disclosed violations span the Clean Air Act, Clean Water Act, Resource Conservation and Recovery Act, and other environmental statutes¹⁴⁹. The program demonstrates how personalized enforcement, properly

¹⁴⁴ Incentives for Self-Policing: Discovery, Disclosure, Correction and Prevention of Violations, 65 Fed. Reg. 19,618, 19,621-25 (Apr. 11, 2000) (establishing nine conditions for penalty mitigation, including requirements relating to voluntary discovery, prompt disclosure, remediation, prevention of recurrence, and absence of repeat violations).

¹⁴⁵ See *EPA's Audit Policy*, EPA (Oct. 8, 2025), <https://www.epa.gov/compliance/epas-audit-policy> [https://perma.cc/E4G4-2UCD].

¹⁴⁶ See 65 Fed. Reg. at 19,625 (Condition D.7, providing that a disclosed violation must not be a “repeat violation,” defined as one that is “the same or closely related to” a violation identified at the same facility within the past three years, and that failure to satisfy this condition renders the entity ineligible for elimination of gravity-based penalties).

¹⁴⁷ See Short & Toffel, *supra* note 81, at 49.

¹⁴⁸ Office of Enf't & Compliance Assurance, *EPA Celebrates Key Anniversaries by Releasing Updated Audit Policy FAQs*, EPA (Mar. 2021), <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2021-03/documents/auditpolicyprogramspotlight.pdf> [https://perma.cc/M9HY-CE5F].

¹⁴⁹ See Incentives for Self-Policing: Discovery, Disclosure, Correction and Prevention of Violations, 65 Fed. Reg. 19618, 19620-21 (Apr. 11, 2000) (identifying the range of environmental statutes covered by the Audit Policy, including the Clean Air Act, Clean Water Act, and Resource Conservation and Recovery Act, and specifying the conditions under which penalty mitigation is available for voluntarily disclosed violations under each statute).

structured with clear criteria and graduated consequences, can achieve greater environmental protection than purely deterrent approaches¹⁵⁰.

The EPA also employs advanced monitoring and predictive analytics to differentiate among regulated entities. The agency uses continuous emissions monitoring systems, remote sensing data, and self-reported discharge information to identify behavioral patterns suggesting elevated violation risk.¹⁵¹ Facilities demonstrating consistent reporting, stable operational patterns aligned with permit terms, and proactive remediation of identified issues receive less frequent inspections¹⁵². Conversely, facilities showing anomalous operational patterns, reporting irregularities, or violations triggering enforcement actions face enhanced scrutiny through targeted inspections and continuous monitoring requirements¹⁵³.

The SEC developed multiple programs that differentiate entities based on compliance history and cooperative behavior¹⁵⁴. The SEC Cooperation Program, announced in 2010 and

¹⁵⁰ See Short & Toffel, *supra* note 87, at 55-58 (finding that the EPA's Audit Policy generated substantially more violation disclosures and corrective actions than traditional deterrence-based enforcement alone, and that firms participating in voluntary disclosure programs corrected violations more quickly and comprehensively than firms subject to standard enforcement proceedings).

¹⁵¹ See Miyuki Hino, Elinor Benami & Nina Brooks, *Machine Learning for Environmental Monitoring*, 1 NATURE SUSTAINABILITY 583, 584, 586 (2018).

¹⁵² See Hino, Benami & Brooks, *supra* note 148, at 586-88 (describing how environmental agencies use continuous monitoring data and predictive analytics to allocate inspection resources, directing less frequent oversight toward facilities with consistent reporting records and stable operational patterns aligned with permit conditions).

¹⁵³ See *id.* at 588-90 (documenting how anomalous emissions patterns, reporting irregularities, and prior enforcement actions trigger enhanced regulatory scrutiny, including increased inspection frequency and requirements for continuous monitoring equipment).

¹⁵⁴ See Leone, Li & Liu, *supra* note 123, at 3-5 (describing the SEC's development of multiple programs that use compliance history and cooperative behavior as the basis for differentiated

formalized through subsequent enforcement guidance, provides credit in enforcement proceedings for entities that self-report violations, provide substantial cooperation in investigations, and implement meaningful remedial measures.¹⁵⁵ The program creates explicit incentives for voluntary disclosure by offering reduced penalties, deferred prosecution agreements, or declinations to prosecute depending on cooperation quality and timeliness¹⁵⁶.

The program differentiates based on behavioral indicators. Maximum cooperation credit requires self-reporting before the SEC discovers the violation through other means¹⁵⁷. Cooperation after SEC-initiated investigation receives lesser credit¹⁵⁸. Entities with compliance programs demonstrating effectiveness receive greater credit than those with merely paper programs.¹⁵⁹ Most importantly, the SEC considers cooperation history. Recidivists or entities

enforcement treatment, including cooperation credit in enforcement proceedings and risk-based surveillance systems).

¹⁵⁵ See *Enforcement Cooperation Program*, U.S. SEC. & EXCH. COMM'N, DIVISION OF ENFORCEMENT (2010), <https://www.sec.gov/spotlight/enforcement-cooperation-initiative.shtml> [<https://perma.cc/7D5W-X5A7>].

¹⁵⁶ See *Enforcement Cooperation Program*, *supra* note 155 (establishing a formal framework for granting reduced penalties, deferred prosecution agreements, or declinations to prosecute based on the quality, completeness, and timeliness of an entity's self-reporting and cooperation).

¹⁵⁷ See Leone, Li & Liu, *supra* note 124, at 10-12 (documenting the SEC's graduated cooperation credit system, under which maximum credit is reserved for entities that self-report violations before the SEC initiates an independent investigation).

¹⁵⁸ See *id.* at 12-14 (finding that the SEC assigns diminishing cooperation credit as the timing of disclosure moves further from initial self-reporting toward cooperation only after investigation has commenced).

¹⁵⁹ See Leone, Li & Liu, *supra* note 124, at 19.

with patterns of misconduct receive reduced benefits regardless of current cooperation, while first-time violators with otherwise clean records receive maximum consideration¹⁶⁰.

For market surveillance, the SEC employs sophisticated behavioral recognition technologies. The Advanced Relational Trading Enforcement Metrics Investigation System analyzes patterns across billions of trading records to identify suspicious activity.¹⁶¹ The system flags entities whose trading patterns match known manipulation techniques, including spoofing, layering, and wash trading. The system assigns risk scores based on historical trading behavior, enabling targeted investigations of high-risk actors while reducing examination burdens on compliant market participants¹⁶².

The SEC also operates systems using machine learning to detect first-time insider trading violations by identifying trading patterns that deviate from normal behavior immediately before market-moving announcements.¹⁶³ These systems demonstrate how regulatory agencies can

¹⁶⁰ *See id.* at 17-19 (analyzing how the SEC weighs compliance history in determining cooperation credit, with recidivist entities and those with patterns of prior misconduct receiving reduced benefits regardless of the quality of their current cooperation, while first-time violators with otherwise clean records receive maximum consideration).

¹⁶¹ Statement from Mary Jo White, Chair, SEC, Remarks at the International Institute for Securities Market Growth and Development (Apr. 8, 2016), <https://www.sec.gov/newsroom/speeches-statements/statement-mjw-040816> [<https://perma.cc/K4GQ-PGQ6>]. (describing the SEC's use of advanced data analytics and surveillance tools to identify suspicious trading activity and focus enforcement resources more effectively)

¹⁶² *Id.*

¹⁶³ *See* Daniel M. Hawke, *SEC Data Analysis in Insider Trading Investigations*, CLS BLUE SKY BLOG (Aug. 21, 2019), <https://clsbluesky.law.columbia.edu/2019/08/21/sec-data-analysis-in-insider-trading-investigations/> [<https://perma.cc/TFT2-6HND>].

employ behavioral pattern recognition to differentiate between trustworthy and suspicious actors without relying on crude categorical distinctions¹⁶⁴.

The FDA's VQIP, established under the Food Safety Modernization Act of 2011, creates an expedited import review process for food importers with demonstrated safety records.¹⁶⁵ Program participants receive expedited review and release of food shipments, reduced physical examination rates, and importation of foods before FDA review, conditional on demonstrated compliance with food safety standards¹⁶⁶.

Eligibility requires stringent compliance history. Importers must demonstrate that foreign suppliers operate under food safety systems comparable to U.S. requirements, have passed recent foreign government or third-party audits, and have no history of significant FDA violations.¹⁶⁷ The program continuously monitors participant performance: any FDA refusal of entry, warning letter, or serious compliance issue triggers immediate removal from the program and reversion to

¹⁶⁴ See Hawke, *supra* note 110 (arguing that the SEC's machine learning systems represent a shift from categorical enforcement approaches toward individualized behavioral assessment, enabling regulators to distinguish trustworthy from suspicious actors based on observed conduct rather than crude proxies).

¹⁶⁵ FDA Food Safety Modernization Act, Pub. L. No. 111-353, § 806, 124 Stat. 3885, 3954–56 (2011) (codified at 21 U.S.C. § 384b).

¹⁶⁶ See FDA Food Safety Modernization Act § 806, 124 Stat. at 3954-56 (establishing the VQIP framework and specifying that participating importers receive expedited review, reduced physical examination rates, and the ability to import food products prior to FDA review, conditional on demonstrated compliance with applicable food safety standards).

¹⁶⁷ *Voluntary Qualified Importer Program*, FDA (2022), <https://www.fda.gov/food/importing-food-products-united-states/voluntary-qualified-importer-program-vqip> (on file with the American University Business Law Review).

standard import procedures¹⁶⁸. This creates powerful incentives for sustained compliance to maintain expedited processing benefits¹⁶⁹.

The FDA also employs risk-based inspection frequency for domestic facilities. The Food Safety Modernization Act mandates risk-based inspections, requiring the FDA to inspect high-risk facilities more frequently than low-risk facilities.¹⁷⁰ The agency assigns risk categories based on food type, processing methods, compliance history, and previous inspection findings. Facilities with serious violations or repeated noncompliance face annual or more frequent inspections, while facilities with clean records may face inspection only every five to seven years.¹⁷¹ This differentiated approach enables the FDA to allocate limited inspection resources toward highest-risk facilities while reducing burdens on compliant operators.

Customs and Border Protection (“CBP”) administers multiple programs that differentiate importers based on compliance history rather than treating all market participants identically. The Customs-Trade Partnership Against Terrorism (C-TPAT), established after September 11, 2001, offers expedited processing and reduced examination rates for importers that demonstrate

¹⁶⁸ See FDA Food Safety Modernization Act § 421, 124 Stat. at 3923-24 (mandating that the FDA assign risk categories to domestic food facilities based on the type of food processed, the facility's compliance history, and the inherent risk of the manufacturing process, with high-risk facilities subject to inspection every three years and other facilities inspected every five to seven years).

¹⁶⁹ See *Voluntary Qualified Importer Program*, *supra* note 166 (specifying that any FDA refusal of entry, warning letter, import alert, or other significant compliance failure triggers immediate removal from VQIP and reversion to standard import review procedures, creating strong incentives for participants to maintain continuous compliance).

¹⁷⁰ See *supra* note 168.

¹⁷¹ See FDA Food Safety Modernization Act § 201, 124 Stat. at 3885–86 (codified at 21 U.S.C. § 350j).

secure supply-chain practices.¹⁷² Certification requires comprehensive security assessments, regular audits, and a demonstrated commitment to supply-chain security, and participating firms receive tangible operational benefits, including priority processing and reduced inspections¹⁷³.

The program differentiates explicitly on behavioral grounds through a tiered certification system. Tier 1 members receive basic benefits upon initial certification. Tier 2 members, who undergo validation of security practices through CBP site visits and demonstrate sustained compliance over time, receive enhanced benefits, including further reductions in examination rates.¹⁷⁴ Tier 3 members, who maintain consistently strong compliance records and participate in additional security initiatives, receive the most extensive benefits. Importantly, violations or security incidents trigger immediate tier reduction or removal, preserving the credibility of the program's trust-based design¹⁷⁵.

CBP also operates the Importer Self-Assessment program, allowing qualified importers to self-assess their compliance with customs requirements in exchange for reduced CBP oversight.¹⁷⁶ Participation requires sophisticated internal compliance systems, comprehensive

¹⁷² *Customs Trade Partnership Against Terrorism (CTPAT)*, U.S. CUSTOMS & BORDER PROT., <https://www.cbp.gov/border-security/ports-entry/cargo-security/ctpat> [<https://perma.cc/V5W7-PDHD>] (last visited Feb. 14, 2026).

¹⁷³ *See* SAFE Port Act, Pub. L. No. 109-347, §§ 214–216, 120 Stat. 1884, 1908–09 (2006).. (describing the certification requirements, including comprehensive security assessments and regular audits, and the operational benefits available to certified participants, including priority processing at ports of entry and reduced rates of physical inspection).

¹⁷⁴ *See id.*

¹⁷⁵ *See id.* (explaining the tiered benefit structure and the consequences of noncompliance, including that security incidents or violations of program requirements trigger immediate tier reduction or suspension of benefits, preserving the integrity of the trust-based certification system).

¹⁷⁶ *See* U.S. CUSTOMS AND BORDER PROT., IMPORTER SELF-ASSESSMENT HANDBOOK 1 (2011), https://www.cbp.gov/sites/default/files/documents/isa_hb_3.pdf [<https://perma.cc/CJ8W-KC2H>].

supply-chain reviews, and sustained transparency with the agency. Together, these programs illustrate how differentiated oversight can reduce enforcement costs while maintaining compliance through structured, revocable trust rather than blanket deregulation¹⁷⁷.

The Occupational Safety and Health Administration’s (“OSHA”) Voluntary Protection Program (“VPP”), established in 1982, represents one of the earliest federal initiatives in personalized corporate regulation. The VPP recognizes employers demonstrating exemplary workplace safety and health management systems.¹⁷⁸ Participants must develop comprehensive safety programs, demonstrate injury and illness rates below industry averages, and commit to employee involvement in safety management. In exchange, OSHA removes sites from programmed inspection lists, conducting focused verification visits instead of comprehensive inspections.

The program creates graduated recognition levels. Star designation—the highest level—requires demonstration of sustained safety performance, management commitment, employee participation, and systematic hazard analysis and control.¹⁷⁹ Merit participants work toward Star status while demonstrating commitment to improvement. Demonstration participants test new

¹⁷⁷ See *id.*, 3-5 (2011). (describing the ISA program's requirements for sophisticated internal compliance systems and sustained transparency, and explaining how the program reduces enforcement costs by substituting verified self-assessment for direct CBP oversight while maintaining accountability through periodic validation and the threat of program removal).

¹⁷⁸ See OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY & HEALTH ADMIN., *Voluntary Protection Programs*, DEP’T OF LAB., <https://www.osha.gov/vpp> [https://perma.cc/5NXL-XFEF] (last visited Feb. 14, 2026).

¹⁷⁹ See OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY & HEALTH ADMIN., *OSHA Instruction*, CSP 03-01-003, at 7, 21, 23, 26–27 https://www.osha.gov/sites/default/files/enforcement/directives/CSP_03-01-003_1.pdf [https://perma.cc/J2RH-K4ZU].

safety approaches. The tiered structure recognizes different levels of safety management maturity while maintaining high standards for maximum regulatory relief¹⁸⁰.

OSHA continuously monitors participants. Sites that experience serious injuries, fatalities, or willful violations face immediate review and potential removal. Annual self-evaluations and triennial OSHA verification visits ensure sustained performance.¹⁸¹ The continuous monitoring creates accountability mechanisms balancing regulatory relief with performance requirements. By 2020, over 2,000 worksites participated, covering hundreds of thousands of workers with demonstrably superior safety outcomes compared to industry averages.¹⁸²

Federal banking regulators employ extensive risk-based examination systems that differentiate institutions based on safety and soundness indicators. The Office of the Comptroller of the Currency, Federal Reserve, and Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation utilize the same rating system to determine examination frequency and intensity. That rating system is known as CAMELS because it assesses Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management capability, Earnings, Liquidity, and Sensitivity to market risk..¹⁸³ Institutions with strong ratings undergo less frequent

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¹⁸¹ *See id.* at 76–77.

¹⁸² *See* Jordan Barab & David Michaels, Comments on VPP Modernization, Docket No. OSHA-2022-0012 (Apr. 14, 2023), <https://www.regulations.gov/document/OSHA-2022-0012-0025> [<https://perma.cc/3Q2A-ZS9G>] (commenting on OSHA’s proposed updates to the Voluntary Protection Programs).

¹⁸³ *See* Uniform Financial Institutions Rating System, 62 Fed. Reg. 752 (Jan. 6, 1997).

examinations, while institutions with weaknesses face continuous monitoring and enhanced supervision¹⁸⁴.

The Federal Reserve's Large Institution Supervision Coordinating Committee oversees the largest banking organizations through continuous monitoring programs that tailor supervisory intensity to each institution's risk profile.¹⁸⁵ Organizations that demonstrate strong risk management, robust internal controls, and consistent regulatory compliance receive less intrusive supervision. Meanwhile, institutions exhibiting control weaknesses or elevated risk profiles face enhanced supervisory programs including more frequent examinations, restrictions on activities, and requirements for remedial action plans.

The Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (“Bureau”) employs risk-based examination prioritization for nonbank financial companies. The Bureau developed a supervision and examination prioritization methodology that considers institution size, complaint volume, prior examination findings, and behavioral indicators suggesting consumer harm risk.¹⁸⁶ Entities with clean compliance records and low consumer complaint rates face less frequent examination, while those with elevated risk indicators receive priority attention. Examination based on risk

¹⁸⁴ See 12 U.S.C. § 1820(d)(4)© (2018) (an institution was found to be “well managed”); 12 U.S.C. § 1841(o)(9) (the definition of “well managed” is a CAMEL (now CAMELS) score of 1 or 2).

¹⁸⁵ See BD. OF GOVERNORS OF FED. RSRV. SYS., SUPERVISION AND REGULATION REPORT 8, 11 (2020).

¹⁸⁶ CONSUMER FIN. PROT. BUREAU, COMPLIANCE MANAGEMENT REVIEW (Version 2) 9–10 (2012), https://files.consumerfinance.gov/f/documents/102012_cfpb_compliance-management-review_supervision-and-examination-manual.pdf [<https://perma.cc/HBE5-74PC>] (discussing risk-based examination prioritization).

enables the Bureau to allocate limited resources toward entities most likely to violate consumer protection laws.

These programs used by different regulatory authorities demonstrate several consistent principles in contemporary personalized corporate regulation. First, differential treatment of the regulator towards the regulated operates through transparent, publicly articulated criteria rather than opaque administrative discretion. Each program establishes clear standards for earning regulatory benefits and equally clear consequences for failing to maintain them¹⁸⁷. Second, this personalization of the regulated focuses on institutional behavior and systems, rather than immutable corporate characteristics. These programs assess a corporation's individual compliance history, management quality, internal controls, and demonstrated commitment to regulatory cooperation. Third, these programs create dynamic rather than static classifications. Corporations move between categories based on ongoing performance, maintaining incentives for sustained compliance while providing pathways for improvement¹⁸⁸.

The programs also reveal important limitations. Participation remains voluntary; thus, only corporations confident in their compliance capabilities opt in. Voluntary opt-in creates selection effects that may overstate program effectiveness. Additionally, most programs serve a

¹⁸⁷ See, e.g., *Compliance Assurance Process*, *supra* note 129 (establishing publicly articulated admission and removal criteria); *Customs Trade Partnership Against Terrorism*, *supra* note 172 (creating a tiered certification system with transparent behavioral standards); Occupational Safety & Health Admin., *Voluntary Protection Programs*, *supra* note 178 (specifying graduated recognition levels with clear performance requirements).

¹⁸⁸ See *supra* Part IV.D.2 (surveying programs across tax, environmental, securities, food safety, customs, occupational safety, and banking regulation, each of which creates dynamic classifications that adjust regulatory treatment based on ongoing corporate performance rather than static categorical assignments).

relatively small number of large and sophisticated corporations rather than the broader universe of regulated corporations. Extension to smaller corporations with fewer resources for compliance systems remains limited. Finally, these programs require substantial administrative capacity for monitoring, verification, and enforcement, which raises questions about scalability¹⁸⁹.

Nonetheless, the proliferation of personalized regulatory programs across diverse domains demonstrates regulatory agencies' practical embrace of differentiated enforcement based on demonstrated trustworthiness. These programs operationalize responsive regulation theories through concrete institutional mechanisms. The Agencies created structured frameworks for earning and maintaining regulatory trust while preserving enforcement capabilities for noncompliant actors. As regulatory agencies face increasing resource constraints alongside expanding regulatory mandates, these models offer templates for efficient, effective enforcement that aligns regulatory burdens with demonstrated risk.

E. ESG and Market Reputation

At the same time, corporations differ from individuals in a crucial countervailing respect: corporations are subject to continuous reputational evaluation by markets, regulators, civil society, and the media. This reputational exposure can impose sanctions that are more severe, faster, and more consequential than formal legal penalties. As a result, corporations may have more to lose from exploiting trust than individuals do. Empirical evidence supports this claim: John Armour, Colin Mayer, and Andrea Polo show that reputational losses following regulatory

¹⁸⁹ See Cary Coglianese & Jennifer Nash, *Performance Track's Postmortem: Lessons from the Rise and Fall of EPA's "Flagship" Voluntary Program*, 38 Harv. Envtl. L. Rev. 1, 44-58 (2014) (finding that EPA's flagship voluntary program failed to demonstrate meaningful environmental gains, attracted participants based more on organizational characteristics than superior performance, and faced structural limits that constrained its broader impact)

enforcement actions routinely exceed the impact of formal sanctions by an order of magnitude. Market capitalization decline, investor exit, and increased cost of capital often dwarf the fines imposed by regulators. In this sense, reputational sanctions function as a powerful quasi-regulatory mechanism, thereby disciplining corporate behavior even where formal enforcement is imperfect.¹⁹⁰

The disciplining effect is amplified by contemporary ESG regimes. Corporations today operate under persistent scrutiny through mandatory disclosures, sustainability reporting, investor stewardship, and third-party ESG ratings.¹⁹¹ Legal violations, governance failures, and ethical lapses are increasingly translated into ESG risk assessments that influence institutional investment decisions. Firms that exploit consumer trust risk exclusion from investment portfolios, consumer boycotts, NGO campaigns, and long-term damage to brand value.¹⁹²

Crucially, these reputational mechanisms operate continuously rather than episodically. Unlike criminal enforcement, which may occur years after misconduct, reputational sanctions often arise immediately upon disclosure. Media exposure, activist campaigns, and social-media amplification can trigger swift and cascading consequences to the corporation. As a result, even

¹⁹⁰ See Armour, Mayer & Polo, *supra* note 91, at 1441–1442 (demonstrating that market reactions to enforcement actions frequently impose reputational costs on firms that exceed formal penalties).

¹⁹¹ See Eccles, Ioannou & Serafeim, *supra* note 92, at 2838, 2841–42, 2853.

¹⁹² See JOHN C. COFFEE JR., GATEKEEPERS: THE PROFESSIONS AND CORPORATE GOVERNANCE 95–110 (2006).

profit-maximizing firms may rationally refrain from opportunistic behavior when they anticipate reputational blowback¹⁹³.

From this perspective, reputation and ESG operate as functional substitutes for intrinsic moral motivation. While corporations may lack conscience, they remain acutely sensitive to signals of trustworthiness. Where reputational loss is salient, transparent, and durable, trust-based regulatory strategies may succeed precisely because trust violations are costly. The hopeful case, then, is not that corporations are more moral actors like individuals, but that markets, investors, and civil society increasingly ensure that betraying trust is bad business¹⁹⁴.

V. A DIFFERENTIATED FRAMEWORK FOR CORPORATE REGULATION

A. Taxonomic Considerations

Neither blanket optimism nor blanket pessimism about corporate voluntary compliance is warranted. Corporations present distinctive challenges for trust-based regulation, but they also possess characteristics that may facilitate such regulation under the appropriate conditions. The task for regulatory policy is to identify those conditions and calibrate regulatory strategies accordingly.

¹⁹³ See Armour, Mayer & Polo, *supra* note 91, at 1435-40 (documenting that market reactions to enforcement disclosures are rapid and often disproportionate to formal penalties, with reputational losses materializing within days of public disclosure and persisting well beyond the resolution of formal proceedings).

¹⁹⁴ See Eccles, Ioannou & Serafeim, *supra* note 92, at 2850-53 (finding that firms with strong sustainability performance outperform peers over the long term, suggesting that the market increasingly rewards trustworthy corporate behavior and penalizes reputational violations through sustained valuation effects rather than episodic sanctions).

To evaluate the effectiveness of voluntary compliance under different legal doctrines, it is important to understand that not all regulatory situations require the same amount of corporate cooperation or intrinsic motivation.¹⁹⁵ One can develop a taxonomy of regulatory contexts by considering factors such as the ease of enforcement, the significance of compliance quality, and the visibility of the regulated behavior.¹⁹⁶ This framework allows for a more nuanced approach to regulatory strategies, acknowledging that in some cases, traditional command-and-control measures may be more appropriate and effective than relying on voluntary compliance.

Several factors should inform the choice between trust-based and enforcement-based approaches in corporate regulation:

Quality of compliance. In regulatory domains where the quality of compliance matters as much as its occurrence, voluntary approaches may be preferable. When corporations comply merely to avoid sanctions, they tend to satisfy minimum requirements without embracing regulatory objectives. Trust-based approaches that foster genuine commitment to compliance goals are more likely to produce high-quality outcomes. Environmental regulation exemplifies this dynamic: simply meeting emission thresholds differs significantly from embracing innovative practices that minimize environmental impact.¹⁹⁷

Feasibility of monitoring. When regulated conduct is easily observable, the case for enforcement-based approaches is stronger; the threat of detection and punishment can effectively deter violations. When monitoring is costly or impossible, trust-based approaches may be the only viable option.¹⁹⁸ Many forms of corporate misconduct, subtle discrimination, corner-cutting on quality, inadequate safety procedures, are difficult to detect externally and may only come to light through voluntary disclosure or whistleblowing.

Cost of compliance failures. In high-stakes domains where compliance failures pose severe risks, nuclear safety, hazardous waste management, financial system stability, regulators may reasonably conclude that the benefits of trust-based approaches do not justify the risks of

¹⁹⁵ See generally FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at ch. 11 (providing an analogy for a similar taxonomy in the context of individual voluntary compliance).

¹⁹⁶ See Yuval Feldman & Orly Lobel, *Behavioral Trade-Offs: Beyond the Land of Nudges Spans the World of Law and Psychology*, in *Handbook of Behavioral Economics and the Law* 301 4, 8 (Eyal Zamir & Doron Teichman eds., 2014).

¹⁹⁷ See *id.* at 28–29.

¹⁹⁸ See Scott M. Gilpatric, Christian A. Vossler & Michael McKee, *Regulatory Enforcement with Competitive Endogenous Audit Mechanisms*, 42 *RAND J. ECON.* 292, 293, 307 (2011).

reduced enforcement.¹⁹⁹ The potential consequences of a single major failure may be catastrophic and irreversible, warranting intensive enforcement even if such enforcement crowds out some intrinsic compliance motivation.

Heterogeneity of regulated population. When regulated corporations vary substantially in their compliance disposition, differentiated approaches become attractive. Trust-based strategies can be directed toward corporations with demonstrated compliance records, while enforcement resources are concentrated on bad actors.²⁰⁰ This differentiation requires the capacity to identify and distinguish compliant from non-compliant corporations.

Repeat-player dynamics. Trust-based approaches are more viable when regulated corporations engage in ongoing relationships with regulators.²⁰¹ One-shot interactions provide insufficient basis for developing the mutual trust that voluntary compliance frameworks require²⁰².

B. Applications Across Regulatory Domains

Applying this framework across different areas of business regulation yields differentiated recommendations. Securities regulation presents a good example: on the one hand, securities markets involve sophisticated corporate actors with strong reputational incentives and repeat-player dynamics. The SEC's cooperation program demonstrates that a trust-based approach can work in this domain.²⁰³ On the other hand, the stakes of securities violations are high, and the complexity of securities law creates ethical blind spots where good-faith compliance is genuinely uncertain. The recommended approach combines voluntary self-reporting programs with continued enforcement capacity.

¹⁹⁹ See FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 259, 262, 268.

²⁰⁰ See *id.*

²⁰¹ See (add source). See generally Braithwaite, *supra* note 20, at (pincite) (explanatory parenthetical).

²⁰² See Ayres & Braithwaite, *supra* note 1, at 19-27 (arguing that the credibility of regulatory escalation depends on repeated interactions between regulators and regulated entities, and that one-shot encounters provide insufficient basis for the cooperative equilibria that responsive regulation requires); see also Feldman, *supra* note 3, at 260-62 (discussing how repeat interactions enable regulators to calibrate trust-based approaches based on observed compliance behavior over time).

²⁰³ See Leone, Li & Liu, *supra* note 124, at 1, 10, 17.

Environmental regulation is particularly well-suited to voluntary compliance approaches. Environmental compliance often requires corporations to go beyond minimum legal requirements, embracing innovative practices that traditional enforcement cannot mandate.²⁰⁴ The EPA’s Audit Policy and programs like Energy Star certification demonstrate how voluntary approaches achieves environmental improvements that command-and-control regulation cannot. Research has shown that non-binding voluntary commitments have a significant, even if limited, impact in encouraging companies to protect the environment.²⁰⁵ Over-reliance on command-and-control regulation can be behaviorally damaging, as there is often a significant gap between simply satisfying the regulatory thresholds and adopting innovative modifications that truly improve corporate environmental behavior.²⁰⁶

Corporate governance presents significant challenges for voluntary compliance. The behavioral ethics concerns discussed in Part II are particularly acute in governance contexts, where conflicts of interest, competitive pressures, and diffused responsibility create conditions favorable to misconduct by otherwise ethical actors.²⁰⁷ John Armour, Jeffrey Gordon, and Geeyoung Min have argued for “taking compliance seriously” as a governance matter,

²⁰⁴ See FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 226–27.

²⁰⁵ See Anne Marike Lokhorst et al., *Commitment and Behavior Change: A Meta-Analysis and Critical Review of Commitment-Making Strategies in Environmental Research*, 45 ENV’T & BEHAV. 3, 24 (2013).

²⁰⁶ See Ann-Kristin Bergquist et al., *Command-and-Control Revisited: Environmental Compliance and Technological Change in Swedish Industry 1970–1990*, 85 ECOLOGICAL ECON. 6, 8, 10, 17 (2013).

²⁰⁷ See Feldman, Libson & Parchomovsky, *supra* note 5, at 1125, 1129–30, 1136, 1139–40, 1182.

emphasizing the need for robust compliance programs that go beyond formal legal requirements.²⁰⁸

C. Technology and Differentiated Enforcement

Advances in regulatory technology create new possibilities for implementing differentiated approaches to corporate regulation. As I discussed in *Can the Public Be Trusted?*,²⁰⁹ This predictive power becomes especially valuable when regulatory approaches rely less on coercion and more on cooperation²¹⁰.

For corporations, technology-enabled differentiation raises fewer normative concerns than it does for individuals. The autonomy-based objections to using past behavior to inform regulatory treatment apply with diminished force to corporate entities.²¹¹ Regulators can more freely employ algorithmic approaches to identify corporations likely to voluntarily comply and direct their trust-based approaches toward those corporations, while concentrating enforcement resources on corporations with poor compliance histories. Trust relationships are inherently reciprocal, when regulators demonstrate trust in corporations, those corporations often respond with increased trustworthy behavior²¹².

²⁰⁸ See John Armour, Jeffrey N. Gordon & Geeyoung Min, *Taking Compliance Seriously*, 37 YALE J. ON REG. 1, 5, 10 (2020).

²⁰⁹ FELDMAN, *supra* note 3, at 171.

²¹⁰ See *id.*, at 170-73 (examining how advances in regulatory technology enable predictive assessment of individual and group compliance behavior, creating the capacity for differentiated enforcement that directs trust-based approaches toward likely compliers while concentrating coercive resources on higher-risk actors).

²¹¹ See *ibid.*

²¹² See Frédérique Six, *Trust in Regulatory Relations: How New Insights from Trust Research Improve Regulation Theory*, 15 Pub. Mgmt. Rev. 163, 170-75 (2013) (analyzing how regulatory trust is inherently reciprocal, such that regulators who demonstrate trust in regulated entities

This technological capacity enables what has been called “watchful trust” in regulatory regimes, an approach that balances trust-based and control-based strategies.²¹³ Under watchful trust, regulators maintain a foundation of trust in regulated entities while implementing specific monitoring mechanisms. The monitoring is designed to verify, rather than substitute, intrinsic compliance motivation, preserving the benefits of voluntary compliance while guarding against its abuse.²¹⁴

D. Algorithmic Regulation and Corporate Trust

As regulators discuss the potential of algorithms to help with trust issues, it is important to recognize that there has already been an increase of research on algorithmic regulation.²¹⁵ In her influential analysis of algorithmic regulation, Karen Yeung examines how automated decision-making systems manage risk and shape behavior through continuous data collection and computational analysis. She develops a comprehensive taxonomy, distinguishing between reactive and preemptive systems, while identifying distinct regulatory forms based on standard setting, information gathering and monitoring, and enforcement through sanctions and behavioral modification²¹⁶.

through reduced oversight signal respect for their compliance efforts, which in turn reinforces cooperative behavior and strengthens the regulatory relationship).

²¹³ See Koen Verhoest et al., *How Trust Matters for the Performance and Legitimacy of Regulatory Regimes: The Differential Impact of Watchful Trust and Good-Faith Trust*, 19 REG. & GOVERNANCE 1, 2, 5 (2024).

²¹⁴ See Frédérique Six, *Trust in Regulatory Relations: How New Insights from Trust Research Improve Regulation Theory*, 15 PUB. MGMT. REV. 163, 165, 170, 179 (2013).

²¹⁵ See Karen Yeung, *Algorithmic Regulation: A Critical Interrogation*, 12 REG. & GOVERNANCE 505–06, 517, 519 (2017).

²¹⁶ See *id.*, at 510-17 (developing a taxonomy of algorithmic regulation that distinguishes reactive systems, which respond to detected violations, from preemptive systems, which anticipate and shape behavior before violations occur, and identifying distinct regulatory forms based on

However, technology-enabled differentiation also poses risks. These concerns are particularly evident when automated enforcement affects compliance and trust. While technology offers the promise of more efficient and consistent enforcement, research indicates it may erode public trust, creating new challenges for voluntary compliance.²¹⁷ New technologies amplify existing inequities if not carefully designed and implemented.²¹⁸ Recognizing these systemic risks, researchers are developing comprehensive frameworks to evaluate the impact of regulatory technologies before deployment.

The justification for using predictive analytics varies by policy context. Stronger interventions might be warranted for objectives of higher public importance. This aligns with the constitutional proportionality doctrine, which permits greater regulatory action when pursuing objectives of higher public importance.²¹⁹ The challenge is to deploy technological capabilities in ways that enhance, rather than undermine, the trust relationships that voluntary compliance depends upon.

VI. CONCLUSION

This Article has examined whether the voluntary compliance framework developed with regards to individuals in *Can the Public Be Trusted?* can extend to corporate regulation. The

standard setting, information gathering, and behavioral modification through automated sanctions or incentives).

²¹⁷ See Lyria Bennett Moses & Janet Chan, *Algorithmic Prediction in Policing: Assumptions, Evaluation, and Accountability*, 28 POLICING & SOC'Y 806 (2018).

²¹⁸ See Solon Barocas & Andrew D. Selbst, *Big Data's Disparate Impact*, 104 CAL. L. REV. 671, 688–89, 729 (2016).

²¹⁹ See OMRI BEN-SHAHAR & ARIEL PORAT, PERSONALIZED LAW: DIFFERENT RULES FOR DIFFERENT PEOPLE (2021). Better suited here: Aronson, Ori and Feldman, Yuval and Lobel, Orly, Behavioral Recognition Technology (February 02, 2026). Indiana Law Journal, Volume 102, forthcoming, 2026.

answer is neither a simple yes nor a simple no; rather, it requires a differentiated framework that identifies the conditions under which trust-based approaches are most likely to succeed.

Corporations present distinctive challenges for trust-based regulation. Their instrumental orientation, the behavioral ethics challenges of organizational contexts, and structural impediments to intrinsic motivation all suggest caution in extending voluntary compliance approaches to business entities. The insights from *The Law of Good People* and *Corporate Law for Good People* demonstrate that organizational settings can amplify, rather than mitigate, the cognitive biases and self-serving rationalizations that lead to misconduct. The disparity between perceived and actual motivations raises serious concerns about the reliability of self-regulation, especially under conditions of limited monitoring²²⁰.

Yet corporations also possess characteristics that may facilitate trust-based regulation: reputational sensitivity, repeat-player dynamics, bureaucratic transparency, richer compliance data, and the absence of autonomy-based constraints on differentiated treatment. As our ongoing work with Aronson and Lobel demonstrates, these attributes make corporations ideal starting points for algorithmic trust assessment systems. Agencies can develop and refine predictive trust technologies in corporate contexts before extending them to individuals, where privacy and dignity concerns loom larger. The success of existing voluntary compliance programs in

²²⁰ See *supra* Part III (examining how the instrumental orientation of corporate decision-making, behavioral ethics challenges in organizational contexts, and structural impediments to intrinsic motivation create distinctive obstacles to trust-based corporate regulation).

securities, environmental, tax, and food safety regulation demonstrate that trust-based approaches can work with corporations under appropriate conditions²²¹.

The framework developed in this Article suggests that the appropriate regulatory approach depends on contextual factors: the importance of compliance quality, the feasibility of monitoring, the stakes of compliance failures, the heterogeneity of the regulated population, and the presence of repeat-player dynamics. Rather than banning AI-driven regulatory tools completely or embracing them without limits, a middle path through differential administrative burden appears most promising. Agencies should create systems where trustworthy actors face lighter reporting requirements, faster permits, and fewer inspections, while maintaining strong oversight of higher-risk subjects. This differential treatment, based on individual corporation's past behavior vis-à-vis regulators, rather than on demographics or other class markers, can improve both efficiency and fairness without creating harm to the social fabric of society²²².

Three implications follow for regulatory policy and legal scholarship:

First, regulators should resist the temptation to treat corporate voluntary compliance as either a panacea or an impossibility. The evidence reviewed in this Article supports neither view. Instead, regulators should develop differentiated strategies that deploy trust-based approaches where they are likely to succeed while maintaining robust enforcement capacity for contexts where they are not.

Second, legal scholarship should attend more carefully to the behavioral ethics dynamics of corporate compliance. The insights from behavioral ethics research have significant

²²¹ See *supra* Part IV.D (surveying trust-based compliance programs across securities, environmental, tax, food safety, customs, occupational safety, and banking regulation, and identifying the institutional design features associated with program effectiveness).

²²² See Aronson, Feldman & Lobel, *supra* note 104 (arguing that differential regulatory treatment based on individual corporate compliance history, rather than on demographic or categorical classifications, avoids the constitutional and normative concerns associated with group-based profiling while improving both regulatory efficiency and fairness).

implications for corporate law and regulation that have not been fully incorporated into existing theoretical frameworks.

Third, the emergence of technology-enabled differentiation creates both opportunities and risks for corporate regulation. Regulators can now more precisely identify corporations amenable to trust-based approaches and concentrate enforcement resources where they are most needed. But they must deploy these capabilities in ways that preserve rather than undermine the relational trust that voluntary compliance depends upon.

Ultimately, the question *Can Corporations be Trusted?* admits no universal answer. Like individuals, corporations vary in their compliance dispositions, and like individual compliance, corporate compliance depends on a complex interplay of motivations, capabilities, and contextual factors. The contribution of this Article is to identify the relevant factors and provide a framework for calibrating regulatory approaches to the specific conditions of different corporate contexts.